

Soundness proof of type checking

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B1 Commentary

Since Core is a first-order language, and we require that all functions and labels are annotated with the correct type, it suffices to only use purely syntactic techniques to prove soundness. This remains true despite the addition of linear types, systems with which are normally proved using logical relations. There are three main components to this: a joint progress-and-type-preservation proof for resource term reduction, a progress theorem and a type-preservation theorem.

Let a resource be called *normalised* if it is either a *pred*, *qpred* or an under-determined conditional resource. Let a resource context $\underline{\mathcal{R}}$ be called normalised if it contains only normalised resources. Even though the grammar of resources is richer, we can, in all the proofs relating to well-typed closed resource terms, assume the resource context to be normalised. This is fine because of the following lemma: if a well-typed resource term is closed, then the context in which it is well-typed must be normalised.

Operational semantics for resource term happens to be defined using big-step style; this makes its definition concise and modular, at the cost of making the proof of soundness of resource term reduction more complicated since it requires joint progress and type preservation. The configuration for the operational semantics is a pair of a heap and an annotated and let-normalised Core program.

Heaps only contain normalised resources. Predicates in heaps are optionally tagged with their “definition” *def* (a resource value of the type of the predicate body) and a sub-heap (of the resources used by the definition). This is to support folding and unfolding predicates in the operational semantics, and to capture the idea that predicate encapsulate their contents until opened.

$$\frac{\text{pred} \equiv \text{pred_term}(\text{oarg}) \quad \langle h + h'; \text{res_pat} = \text{def} \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h''; \sigma \rangle}{\langle h + \{\text{pred} \ \& \ \text{def} \ \& \ h'\}; \text{fold}(\text{res_pat}) = \text{pred_term} \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h''; \sigma \rangle}$$

$$\frac{\text{pred} \equiv \text{pred_term}(\text{oarg}) \quad \langle h; \text{res_term} \rangle \Downarrow \langle h_1; \text{def} \rangle \quad \text{footprint_of } \text{def} \text{ in } h_1 \rightsquigarrow h_2 \text{ rem } h_3}{\langle h; \text{fold } \text{res_term} : \text{pred} \rangle \Downarrow \langle h_3 + \{\text{pred} \ \& \ \text{def} \ \& \ h_2\}; \text{pred_term} \rangle}$$

The types of heaps are normalised contexts; the rules for these are straightforward, except the fact a heap with a folded predicate requires there exists a context for which the resource value *def* and *heap* is well-typed. This becomes necessary for proving the progress of pattern-matching for the whole of the annotated and let-normalised Core.

Theorem 1 (Progress and type preservation for resource terms) *For all closed resource terms (res_term) which type check or synthesise ($\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{res_term} \Leftarrow \text{res}$) and all well-typed heaps ($\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}$) there exists a resource value (res_val), context ($\underline{\mathcal{R}}'$) and heap (h'), such that: the value is well-typed ($\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \text{res_val} \Leftarrow \text{res}$); the heap is well-typed ($\Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$); for all frame-heaps (f), the resource term reduces to the resource value without affecting the frame-heap ($\langle h + f; \text{res_term} \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + f; \text{res_val} \rangle$).*

The interesting case in the proof of this is folding a predicate; proving this case requires a notion of *footprint* of a resource value: the subheap containing the resources referred to by the value.

Theorem 2 (Progress for the annotated and let-normalised Core) *If a top-level expression (texpr) is well-typed ($\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{texpr} \Leftarrow \text{ret}$) and all computational patterns in it are exhaustive, then either it is a value (tval), or it is unreachable, or for all heaps (h), if the heap is well-typed ($\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}$) then there exists another heap (h') and expression (texpr') which is stepped to ($\langle h; \text{texpr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; \text{texpr}' \rangle$) in the operational semantics.*

The assumption that all computational patterns are exhaustive is justified because they are generated by Cerberus. As one might expect, proving progress requires well-typed patterns successfully produce substitutions. However, this is complicated by two things, the solution to which requires the introduction of a relation on SMT terms and resource types, $\Phi \vdash res \sim res'$ (to be read “under constraints Φ , res is related to res' ”).

The first is that the constraint term generated when typing a computational pattern (this is required to record, in the constraint context, which branch the type system is assuming it is in) is not exactly equal to the values it can match in the operational semantics (nor would we want it to be: the pattern $\mathbf{Cons}(x_1, x_2)$ should match the value $\mathbf{Cons}(pval_1, \mathbf{Cons}(pval_2, \mathbf{Nil} \beta()))$). Hence, we must weaken the notion of equality on types to \sim relatedness, which links the two, so that during the proof can substitute the constraint term $x_1 :: x_2$ at the type-level, and maintain a link to the corresponding value. The second is that the conditions of related conditional resource must remain SMT-equivalent (with reference to a constraint context), so that pattern-match typing and resource term typing are consistent.

Theorem 3 (Type preservation for the annotated and let-normalised Core) *For all closed and well-typed top-level expressions $(\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{expr} \Leftarrow \text{ret})$, well typed heaps $(\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}})$, frame-heaps (f) , new heaps (heap) , and new top-level expressions (expr') , which are connected by a step in the operational semantics $(\langle h + f; \text{expr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{heap}; \text{expr}' \rangle)$, if all top-level functions are annotated correctly, there exists a constraint context (Φ') , sub-heap (h') , and resource context $(\underline{\mathcal{R}}')$, such that the constraint context is Φ extended, the frame is unaffected $(\text{heap} = h' + f)$, the sub-heap is well-typed $(\Phi' \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}')$, and the top-level expression too $(\cdot; \cdot; \Phi'; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \text{expr}' \Leftarrow \text{ret})$.*

A few things are noteworthy about the proof. First is that a frame-heap has to be explicitly passed around. Whilst this is inconvenient, it becomes necessary in the `EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LET` case. The next is that proof that well-typed spines produce well-typed substitutions require quantifying over the substitutions done *so far*, so that the inductive case matches up *and* the substitution so far ψ shows up in the conclusion, ‘closing’ otherwise ‘open’ substitution and terms. One more is in the proof that well-typed patterns produce well-typed substitutions: unfortunately quantifying over the substitutions done so far is not helpful because *even the substitution itself* can be ‘open’ (refer to free variables). Hence the peculiar typing of pattern-matching, so that all terms are well-scoped. This allows us to induct usefully, and get the required substitution in the output substitution and its type, making way to apply the substitution lemma afterwards. Lastly, we gather constraints throughout the proof, since these are accumulated by the typing rules, during pattern- matching, case and if. Given the constraint context is always well-formed (w.r.t. to the empty contexts), this means that all the constraints must be trivial (though extra effort would be required to show that they are trivially true, for example, showing that `default bool` cannot occur).

B2 Typing Judgements

In this document, $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash J$ stands for all *defined* judgements, listed in the remainder of this section after this paragraph. In particular, it does not stand for $\mathcal{C} \vdash mem_val \Rightarrow \beta$ or $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash term \Rightarrow \beta$. Furthermore, I assume that lemma B6 (Weakening) and lemma B7.3 (Substitution) (proven for the *defined* judgements in the referenced sections) hold for these $(\mathcal{C} \vdash mem_val \Rightarrow \beta)$, and $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash term \Rightarrow \beta$) judgements.

res_judge ::=

- | $\Phi \vdash \mathbf{cmp_min}(iguard, iguard') \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{opt_cmp_term}$
given constraints Φ , *iguard* is potentially included in *iguard'* (or vice-versa) with ordering and minimum *opt_cmp_term*
- | $\Phi \vdash \mathbf{qpred_term} \sqsubseteq? \mathbf{qpred_term}' \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{opt_cmp}$
given constraints Φ , *qpred_term* is potentially included in *qpred_term'* (or vice-versa) with ordering *opt_cmp*
- | $\Phi \vdash \mathbf{res_req} \equiv \mathbf{res_req}' \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{bool}$
resource equality: given constraints Φ , *res_req* and *res_req'* are equal according to *bool*
- | $\Phi \vdash \mathbf{res} \equiv \mathbf{res}'$
resource equality: given constraints Φ , *res* is equal to *res'*
- | $\Phi \vdash \mathbf{simp_rec}(res) \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{res}', \mathbf{bool}$
partial-simplification of resources: given constraints Φ , *res* partially simplifies (strips ifs) to *res'*
- | $\Phi \vdash \mathbf{simp}(res) \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{opt_res}$
partial-simplification of resources: given constraints Φ , *res* attempts a partial simplification (strips ifs) to *opt_res*

ret_judge ::=

- | $\Phi \vdash \mathbf{ret} \equiv \mathbf{ret}'$
return type equality: given constraints Φ , *ret* is equal to *ret'*

pat_judge ::=

- | $\mathbf{pat}:\beta \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{C \ with \ term}$
computational pattern to context: *pat* and type β produces context *C* and constraint *term*
- | $\mathbf{ident_or_pat}:\beta \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{C \ with \ term}$
identifier-or-pattern to context: *ident_or_pat* and type β produces context *C* and constraint *term*

		$\mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{res_pat} : \text{res} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$
		resources pattern to context: given constraints Φ , res_pat of type res produces contexts $\mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$
		$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{ret_pat} : \text{ret} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$
		return pattern to context: given context $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi$, ret_pat and return type ret produces contexts $\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$
		$\Phi \vdash \text{ret_pat} : \text{ret} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$
		return pattern to context: given constraints Φ , ret_pat and return type ret produces contexts $\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$
expl_pure	::=	
		$\mathcal{C} \vdash \text{object_value} \Rightarrow \beta$
		object value synthesises: given \mathcal{C} , object_value synthesises type β
		$\mathcal{C} \vdash \text{pval} \Rightarrow \beta$
		pure value synthesises: given \mathcal{C} , pval synthesises type β
		$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{pexpr} \Rightarrow \text{pure_ret}$
		pure expression synthesises: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi$, pexpr synthesises a pure (non-resourceful) return type pure_ret
		$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{tpval} \Leftarrow \text{pure_ret}$
		pure top-level value checks: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi$, tpval checks against pure_ret
		$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{tpepr} \Leftarrow \text{pure_ret}$
		pure top-level expression checks: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi$, tpepr checks against pure_ret
expl_res	::=	
		$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{pred_ops} \Rightarrow \text{res}$
		resource (q)predicate operation term synthesis: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, pred_ops synthesises resource res
		$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Rightarrow \text{res}$
		resource term synthesises: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, res_term synthesises resource res
		$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Leftarrow \text{res}$
		resource term checks: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, res_term checks against resource res
expl_spine	::=	
		$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{spine} :: \text{fun} \gg \text{ret}$
		function call spine checks: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, compatible spine , fun produces an ret

$expl_is_expr ::=$
| $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash action \Rightarrow ret$
memory action synthesises: given $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$,
 $action$ synthesises return type ret
| $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash memop \Rightarrow ret$
memory operation synthesises: given $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$,
 $memop$ synthesises return type ret
| $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash is_expr \Rightarrow ret$
indet. seq. expression synthesises: given
 $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, is_expr synthesises return type ret

$expl_seq_expr ::=$
| $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash seq_expr \Rightarrow ret$
seq. expression synthesises: given $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$,
 seq_expr synthesises return type ret

$expl_top ::=$
| $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash tval \Leftarrow ret$
top-level value checks: given $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, $tval$
checks against return type ret
| $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash seq_texpr \Leftarrow ret$
top-level seq. expression checks: given $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$,
 seq_texpr checks against return type ret
| $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash is_texpr \Leftarrow ret$
top-level indet. seq. expression checks: given
 $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, is_texpr checks against return type ret
| $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash texpr \Leftarrow ret$
top-level expression checks: given $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$,
 $texpr$ checks against return type ret

B3 Operational Semantics Judgements

<i>subs_judge</i>	$::=$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> $pat = pval \rightsquigarrow \sigma$ computational value deconstruction: pat deconstructs $pval$ to produce substitution σ $ident_or_pat = pval \rightsquigarrow \sigma$ computational value deconstruction: $ident_or_pat$ deconstructs $pval$ to produce substitution σ $\langle h; res_pat = res_val \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h'; \sigma \rangle$ resource term deconstruction: res_pat deconstructs res_val to produce substitution σ $\langle h; \overline{ret_pat_i = ret_term_i^i} \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h'; \sigma \rangle$ return value deconstruction: ret_pat_i deconstructs ret_val_i to produce substitution σ $\langle h; \overline{x_i = spine_elem_i^i} \rangle :: fun \gg \langle h'; \sigma; ret \rangle$ function call spine: heap h and formal parameters x_i assigned to $spine_elem_i$ for function of type fun, produce new heap h' substitution σ and result type ret
<i>pure_opsem_defns</i>	$::=$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> $\langle pexpr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle texpr: pure_ret \rangle$ $\langle texpr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle texpr' \rangle$
<i>opsem_defns</i>	$::=$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> $\langle h; pred_ops \rangle \Downarrow \langle h'; res_val \rangle$ big-step resource (q)points-to operation reduction: $\langle h; pred_ops \rangle$ reduces to $\langle h'; res_val \rangle$ footprint_of res_val in $h \rightsquigarrow h_1$ rem h_2 footprint of res_val in heap h is h_1 with h_2 remainder/frame $\langle h; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h'; res_val \rangle$ big-step resource term reduction: $\langle h; res_term \rangle$ reduces to $\langle h'; res_val \rangle$ $\langle h; action \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; is_expr \rangle$ $\langle h; memop \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; is_expr \rangle$ $\langle h; is_expr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; is_expr' \rangle$ $\langle h; seq_expr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; texpr: ret \rangle$ $\langle h; seq_texpr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; texpr \rangle$ $\langle h; is_texpr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; texpr \rangle$ $\langle h; texpr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; texpr' \rangle$

B4 Proof Judgements

Note that the definition of $term \sim term'$ is omitted/assumed. It simply means that $term$ and $term'$ can be unified. Informally, $term \sim term'$ are defined recursively over the structure of SMT terms, using the standard definition of unification: variables unify with anything (modulo an occurs check), atoms unify if they are identical, compound terms unify if their constructors (except for `Specified`) and arity are identical, and their arguments unify recursively.

To clarify the `Specified` exception: $term \sim \text{Specified}(pval)$ (and $\text{Specified}(pval) \sim term$) iff $term \sim pval$.

\sim is additionally assumed to be an equivalence relation and preserved by substitution: if $term \sim term'$ and $x \sim y$ in $term_1 \sim term'_1$ then $term/x(term_1) \sim term'/y(term'_1)$.

Note: \sim is *only* used in the *proof* of soundness, and *not* in the *explicit CN type system*. There is no unification required in the type system, but the notion of related terms is required to argue for the soundness of pattern-matching (Section B9.4 Well-typed values pattern-match successfully).

misc_extra ::= extra judgements for proof-related definitions
 | $\forall x. \text{iguard} \Rightarrow \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}$
 meta-logical quantification over heap-typing
 | $\forall \text{term} \sim \text{term}'. \Phi \vdash \text{fun} \sim \text{ret}$
 meta-logical quantification over related *fun* and *ret*
 | $\forall \text{term} \sim \text{term}'. \Phi \vdash \text{res} \sim \text{res}'$
 meta-logical quantification over related *res* and *res'*
 | $\text{term} \sim \text{term}'$
 omitted/assumed definition: SMT terms *term* and *term'* are related

proof_defs ::= $\overline{x}_i^i :: \text{fun} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \mid \text{ret}$
 matching \overline{x}_i^i and *fun* produces contexts $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$ and return type *ret*
 | $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \sqsubseteq \mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$
 context weakening: $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$ is stronger than $\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$
 | $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \sigma \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \mathcal{R})$
 well-typed substitution: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, σ checks against type $(\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \mathcal{R})$. It is complicated by the fact that substitutions are assumed to be sequential/telescoping.
 | $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}$
 heap typing: under context $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi$, heap *h* checks against context/type $\underline{\mathcal{R}}$
 | $\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}$
 heap typing: under context Φ , heap *h* checks against context/type $\underline{\mathcal{R}}$
 | $\Phi \vdash \text{res} \sim \text{res}'$
 res is related to *res'*
 | $\Phi \vdash \text{fun} \sim \text{ret}$
 fun is related to *ret*

B5 Groups of Rules

B5.1 Typing rules with an $\text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow qterm)$ premise

IG_CMP_EQ, IG_CMP_LT, IG_CMP_GT, Q_CMP_PTRSTEP_NEQ, Q_CMP_IG_NEQ, Q_CMP_IARG_NEQ, Q_CMP_COMPARABLE, REQ_EQ_PP_IARG_NEQ, REQ_EQ_PP_EQ, RES_EQ_PHI, RES_EQ_ORDDISJ, RES_SIMPREC_IF_TRUE, RES_SIMPREC_IF_FALSE, RET_EQ_PHI, PAT_RES_MATCH_IF_TRUE, PAT_RES_MATCH_IF_FALSE, PURE_EXPR_ASSERT_UNDEF, PURE_TOP_VAL_DONE, PURE_TOP_VAL_UNDEF, PURE_TOP_VAL_ERROR, RES_SYN_PREDOPS_CONGEAL, RES_SYN_PREDOPS_IMPLODE, RES_SYN_PREDOPS_BREAK, RES_SYN_PREDOPS_GLUE, RES_SYN_PREDOPS_INJ, RES_SYN_PREDOPS_SPLIT, RES_CHK_PHI, RES_CHK_IF_TRUE, RES_CHK_IF_FALSE, EXPL_IS_ACTION_LOAD, EXPL_IS_ACTION_STORE, EXPL_IS_ACTION_KILL_STATIC, EXPL_IS_MEMOP_PTRVALIDFORDEREF, EXPL_TOP_VAL_UNDEF, EXPL_TOP_VAL_ERROR.

B5.2 Typing rules which change the context

B5.2.1 Rules which add constraints

EXPL_TOP_SEQ_IF.

B5.2.2 Rules which add constraints and computational or logical variables

EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LETP, EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LETP, EXPL_TOP_SEQ_CASE.

B5.2.3 Rules which restrict the resource context

No-resource / “pure” rules: IG_CMP_EQ, IG_CMP_LT, IG_CMP_GT, IG_CMP_NONE, Q_CMP_NAME_NEQ, Q_CMP_PTRSTEP_NEQ, Q_CMP_IG_NEQ, Q_CMP_IARG_NEQ, Q_CMP_COMPARABLE, REQ_EQ_PP_NAME_NEQ, REQ_EQ_PP_IARG_NEQ, REQ_EQ_PP_EQ, REQ_EQ_QQ_EQ, REQ_EQ_QQ_NEQ, RES_EQ_EMP, RES_EQ_PHI, RES_EQ_PRED, RES_EQ_QPRED, RES_EQ_SEPCONJ, RES_EQ_EXISTS, RES_EQ_ORDDISJ, RES_SIMPREC_IF_TRUE, RES_SIMPREC_IF_FALSE, RES_SIMPREC_SEPCONJ, RES_SIMPREC_EXISTS, RES_SIMPREC_NOCHANGE, SIMP_NO_SIMP, SIMP_SIMP, RET_EQ_END, RET_EQ_COMP, RET_EQ_LOG, RET_EQ_PHI, RET_EQ_RES, PAT_COMP_NO_SYM_ANNOT, PAT_COMP_SYM_ANNOT, PAT_COMP_NIL, PAT_COMP_CONS, PAT_COMP_TUPLE, PAT_COMP_ARRAY, PAT_COMP_SPECIFIED, PAT_SYM_OR_PAT_SYM, PAT_SYM_OR_PAT_PAT, PAT_RES_MATCH_EMP, PAT_RES_MATCH_PHI, PAT_RES_MATCH_IF_TRUE, PAT_RES_MATCH_IF_FALSE, PAT_RES_MATCH_VAR, PAT_RES_MATCH_SEPCONJ, PAT_RES_MATCH_PACK, PAT_RES_MATCH_FOLD, PAT_RET_EMPTY, PAT_RET_COMP, PAT_RET_LOG, PAT_RET_RES, PAT_RET_PHI, PAT_RET'_AUX, PURE_VAL_OBJ_INT, PURE_VAL_OBJ_PTR, PURE_VAL_OBJ_ARR, PURE_VAL_OBJ_STRUCT, PURE_VAL_VAR, PURE_VAL_OBJ, PURE_VAL_LOADED, PURE_VAL_UNIT, PURE_VAL_TRUE, PURE_VAL_FALSE, PURE_VAL_LIST, PURE_VAL_TUPLE, PURE_VAL_CTOR_NIL, PURE_VAL_CTOR_CONS, PURE_VAL_CTOR_TUPLE, PURE_VAL_CTOR_ARRAY, PURE_VAL_CTOR_SPECIFIED, PURE_VAL_STRUCT, PURE_EXPR_VAL, PURE_EXPR_ARRAY_SHIFT, PURE_EXPR_MEMBER_SHIFT, PURE_EXPR_NOT, PURE_EXPR_ARITH_BINOP, PURE_EXPR_REL_BINOP, PURE_EXPR_BOOL_BINOP, PURE_EXPR_CALL, PURE_EXPR_ASSERT_UNDEF, PURE_EXPR_BOOL_TO_INTEGER, PURE_EXPR_WRAP_I, PURE_TOP_VAL_UNDEF, PURE_TOP_VAL_ERROR, PURE_TOP_VAL_DONE.

Resource-mentioning rules: RES_SYN_EMP, RES_SYN_VAR, RES_SYN_VARSIMP, RES_SYN_PRED, RES_SYN_QPRED, RES_SYN_SEPCONJ, RES_CHK_PHI, RES_CHK_SEPCONJ, EXPL_SPINE_RET,

EXPL_SPINE_RES, EXPL_IS_ACTION_CREATE, EXPL_IS_MEMOP_REL_BINOP, EXPL_IS_MEMOP_INTFROMPTR, EXPL_IS_MEMOP_PTRFROMINT, EXPL_IS_MEMOP_PTRVALIDFORDEREF, EXPL_IS_MEMOP_PTRWELLALIGNED, EXPL_IS_MEMOP_INTFROMPTR, EXPL_TOP_VAL_UNDEF, EXPL_TOP_VAL_ERROR, EXPL_TOP_SEQ_RUN, SUBS_CHK_EMPTY, SUBS_CHK_RES.

B5.2.4 Rules which add constraints and restrict the resource context

PURE_TOP_IF.

B5.2.5 Rules which add constraints and variables, and restrict the resource context

PURE_TOP_LET, PURE_TOP_LETT, PURE_TOP_CASE, EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LET, EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LETT, EXPL_TOP_IS_LETS.

B5.3 Value typing rules

PURE_VAL_OBJ_INT, PURE_VAL_OBJ_PTR, PURE_VAL_OBJ_ARR, PURE_VAL_OBJ_STRUCT, PURE_VAL_VAR, PURE_VAL_OBJ, PURE_VAL_LOADED, PURE_VAL_UNIT, PURE_VAL_TRUE, PURE_VAL_FALSE, PURE_VAL_TUPLE, PURE_VAL_CTOR_NIL, PURE_VAL_CTOR_CONS, PURE_VAL_CTOR_TUPLE, PURE_VAL_CTOR_ARRAY, PURE_VAL_CTOR_SPECIFIED, PURE_VAL_STRUCT, PURE_TOP_VAL_DONE, RES_SYN_EMP, RES_SYN_VAR, RES_SYN_VARSIMP, RES_SYN_PRED, RES_SYN_QPRED, RES_CHK_PHI, EXPL_TOP_VAL_DONE.

B6 Weakening

If $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \sqsubseteq \mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$ and $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash J$ then $\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}' \vdash J$.

ASSUME: 1. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \sqsubseteq \mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$.
2. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash J$

PROVE: $\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}' \vdash J$.

$\langle 1 \rangle 1$. CASE: PURE_VAL_VAR.

PROOF: By WEAK_CONS_COMP, if $x:\beta \in \mathcal{C}$ then $x:\beta \in \mathcal{C}'$.

$\langle 1 \rangle 2$. CASE: Typing rules with an $\text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow qterm)$ premise (see B5.1).

ASSUME: $\text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow qterm)$.

PROVE: $\text{smt}(\Phi' \Rightarrow qterm)$.

$\langle 2 \rangle 1$. For all $term$, if $term \in \Phi$ then $term \in \Phi'$.

PROOF: By WEAK_CONS_PHI.

$\langle 2 \rangle 2$. Any extra constraints in Φ' (by WEAK_SKIP_PHI) would either be irrelevant, redundant, or inconsistent.

$\langle 2 \rangle 3$. In all cases, $\text{smt}(\Phi' \Rightarrow qterm)$ as required.

$\langle 1 \rangle 3$. CASE: All remaining rules.

$\langle 2 \rangle 1$. $\mathcal{R} = \mathcal{R}'$.

PROOF: Only WEAK_CONS_RES exists.

$\langle 2 \rangle 2$. All remaining rules are functorial in $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi$, so one can proceed by straightforward induction.

$\langle 2 \rangle 3$. So $\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}' \vdash J$ as required.

B7 Substitution

B7.1 Substitutions preserve SMT results

If $\text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow qterm)$ and $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma(\Phi); \mathcal{R} \vdash \sigma \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \mathcal{R}')$, then $\text{smt}(\sigma(\Phi) \Rightarrow \sigma(qterm))$.

PROOF: By the first assumption, $qterm$ holds for all (well-typed, ensured by the second assumption) instantiations of its free variables.

B7.2 Substitutions can be split up

If $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \sigma \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \mathcal{R}'_1, \mathcal{R}'_2)$ then

$\exists \mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2, \sigma_1, \sigma_2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}_1 \vdash \sigma_1 \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \mathcal{R}'_1) \wedge \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}_2 \vdash \sigma_2 \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \mathcal{R}'_2)$.

PROOF SKETCH: By induction on the substitution. If $\sigma = [res_term/r, \sigma']$ where $r:res$:

(1)1. Let \mathcal{R}' be such that $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}' \vdash res_term \Leftarrow res$.

(1)2. Recursively split σ' into σ'_1 and $\mathcal{R}''_1; \sigma'_2$ and \mathcal{R}''_2 .

(1)3. If $r \in \mathcal{R}'_1$, let $\sigma_1 = [res_term/r, \sigma'_1]$ and $\mathcal{R}_1 = \mathcal{R}', \mathcal{R}''_1$.

(1)4. If $r \in \mathcal{R}'_2$, let $\sigma_2 = [res_term/r, \sigma'_2]$.

(1)5. For other cases, both are treated exactly the same.

B7.3 Substitution

If $\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi; \mathcal{R}' \vdash J$, then $\forall \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \sigma. (\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma(\Phi); \mathcal{R} \vdash \sigma \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \mathcal{R}')) \Rightarrow \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma(\Phi); \mathcal{R} \vdash \sigma(J)$.

For types, substitutions are only defined over resource types res , and return types res , not base types β . Similarly, for terms, substitutions are only defined over expressions (including SMT terms $term$), but not (computational, resource or return) patterns.

Since Φ is scoped to $\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'$, we must substitute over it as well as all the usual suspects on the right.

Substitution of contexts is defined by substituting over each constraint in Φ . As a result, $\sigma(\Phi_1, \Phi_2) = \sigma(\Phi_1), \sigma(\Phi_2)$, and if $\sigma(\Phi) = \Phi'_1, \Phi'_2$ then $\exists \Phi_1, \Phi_2. \sigma(\Phi_1, \Phi_2) = \sigma(\Phi_1), \sigma(\Phi_2)$.

PROOF SKETCH: Induction over the typing judgements.

1. Variable rules: PURE_VAL_VAR, RES_SYN_VARSIMP, RES_SYN_VAR.
2. EXPL_TOP_VAL_DONE: prove that `to_fun` commutes with substitution.
3. Typing rules which change the context (see B5.2).
4. Remaining rules by straightforward induction.

ASSUME: 1. $\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi; \mathcal{R}' \vdash J$.

2. Arbitrary $\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}, \sigma$.

3. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma(\Phi); \mathcal{R} \vdash \sigma \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \mathcal{R}')$.

PROVE: $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma(\Phi); \mathcal{R} \vdash \sigma(J)$.

(1)1. CASE: PURE_VAL_VAR.

$\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}' \vdash x \Rightarrow \beta$

$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma(\Phi); \mathcal{R} \vdash \sigma \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \cdot)$.

(2)1. $x:\beta \in \mathcal{C}'$.

PROOF: By inversion on assumption 1.

(2)2. \mathcal{R} is empty.

PROOF: SUBS_CHK_RES is the only rule which could require a non-empty resource context, and it is never used because \mathcal{R}' is empty.

(2)3. $\exists \sigma_1, pval, \sigma_2, \beta, \mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2, \mathcal{L}_1, \mathcal{L}_2$.

1. $\sigma = [\sigma_1, pval/x, \sigma_2]$

2. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \sigma_1 \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}_1; \cdot)$

3. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \sigma_1(pval/x) \Leftarrow (x:\beta; \cdot; \cdot)$

4. $\mathcal{C} \vdash \sigma_1(pval) \Rightarrow \beta$

5. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \sigma_1(pval/x(\sigma_2)) \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}_2; \mathcal{L}_2; \cdot)$.

PROOF: Repeated inversion on assumption 3 until the SUBS_CHK_COMP responsible for adding x (by (2)1, there must be at least one).

(2)4. Since $\sigma(x) = \sigma_1(pval)$, we are done.

PROOF: By $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash \sigma(x) \Rightarrow \beta$.

(1)2. CASE: RES_SYN_VARSIMP.

$\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi; r:res \vdash r \Rightarrow res'$

$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma(\Phi); \mathcal{R} \vdash \sigma \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; r:res')$.

(2)1. $\exists \sigma_1, res_term, \sigma_2, \mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2, \mathcal{L}_1, \mathcal{L}_2$.

1. $\sigma = [\sigma_1, res_term/r, \sigma_2]$

2. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma(\Phi); \cdot \vdash \sigma_1 \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}_1; \cdot)$

3. $\cdot; \cdot; \sigma(\Phi); \mathcal{R} \vdash \sigma_1(res_term/r) \Leftarrow (\cdot; \cdot; r:\sigma_1(res'))$

4. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma(\Phi); \mathcal{R} \vdash \sigma_1(res_term) \Leftarrow \sigma_1(res')$

5. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma(\Phi); \cdot \vdash \sigma_1(res_term/r(\sigma_2)) \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}_2; \mathcal{L}_2; \cdot)$.

PROOF: Repeated inversion on assumption 3 until the SUBS_CHK_RES responsible for adding r (there must be exactly one).

(2)2. SUFFICES: 1. $\sigma(r) = \sigma_1(res_term)$

2. $\sigma(res') = [\sigma_1, res_term/r, \sigma_2](res') = \sigma_1(res')$.

(2)3. $\sigma(r) = \sigma_1(res_term)$.

PROOF: $\sigma_2(r) = r$, because σ_2 does not mention any resource variables.

(2)4. $\sigma(res') = [\sigma_1, res_term/r, \sigma_2](res') = \sigma_1(res')$.

(3)1. $[\sigma_1, res_term/r, \sigma_2](res') = [\sigma_1, \sigma_2](res')$.

PROOF: Resource types do not refer to resource variables.

(3)2. $[\sigma_1, \sigma_2](res') = \sigma_1(res)$.

PROOF: By $\cdot; \cdot; \sigma(\Phi); \mathcal{R} \vdash \sigma_1(res_term) \Leftarrow \sigma_1(res')$, we know that res' only refers to variables in $\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{L}_1$.

(1)3. CASE: RES_SYN_VAR.

$\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; r:res \vdash r \Rightarrow res$

PROOF: Similar to RES_SYN_VARSIMP, but with $res' = res$.

(1)4. CASE: EXPL_TOP_VAL_DONE.

PROOF SKETCH: `to_fun` recursively maps Σ to Π , \exists to \forall , \wedge to \supset and $*$ to \multimap , and otherwise keeps any *term* and *res* the same. Hence, $\sigma(\text{to_fun } ret) = \text{to_fun } \sigma(ret)$, and the case proceeds by induction straightforwardly.

(1)5. CASE: Typing rules which change the context (see B5.2), except for PURE_VAL_VAR, RES_SYN_VAR, and RES_SYN_VARSIMP.

For brevity, I shall only go over EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LET, as it is one of the most general rules; one which adds constraints and variables, and restricts the resource context.

PROOF SKETCH: The key idea is to apply lemma B7.2 (Substitutions can be split up) as required by the restrictions on the resource context. If a rule has a `smt` ($\Phi \Rightarrow qterm$) premise, then apply lemma B7.1 (Substitutions preserve SMT results).

$\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi; \mathcal{R}'_1, \mathcal{R}'_2 \vdash \text{let } ret_pat = seq_expr \text{ in } texpr \Leftarrow ret_2$

$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma(\Phi); \mathcal{R} \vdash \sigma \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \mathcal{R}'_1, \mathcal{R}'_2)$.

PROVE: $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma(\Phi); \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{let } ret_pat = \sigma(seq_expr) \text{ in } \sigma(texpr) \Leftarrow \sigma(ret_2)$.

(2)1. $\exists ret_1, \mathcal{C}_3, \mathcal{L}_3, \Phi_3, \mathcal{R}_3$.

1. $\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi; \mathcal{R}'_1 \vdash seq_expr \Rightarrow ret_1$

2. $\Phi \vdash ret_pat:ret_1 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_3; \mathcal{L}_3; \Phi_3; \mathcal{R}_3$

3. $\mathcal{C}', \mathcal{C}_3; \mathcal{L}', \mathcal{L}_3; \Phi, \Phi_3; \mathcal{R}'_2, \mathcal{R}_3 \vdash texpr \Leftarrow ret_2$.

PROOF: Inversion on assumption 1.

(2)2. 1. $\forall \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}_1, \sigma_1$.

$(\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma_1(\Phi); \mathcal{R}_1 \vdash \sigma_1 \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \mathcal{R}'_1)) \Rightarrow$

$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma_1(\Phi); \mathcal{R}_1 \vdash \sigma_1(seq_expr) \Rightarrow \sigma_1(ret_1)$.

2. $\forall \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}_4, \sigma_2$.

$(\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma_2(\Phi); \mathcal{R}_4 \vdash \sigma_2 \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \cdot)) \Rightarrow$

$\sigma_2(\Phi) \vdash ret_pat:\sigma_2(ret_1) \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_3; \mathcal{L}_3; \sigma_2(\Phi_3); \sigma_2(\mathcal{R}_3)$.

3. $\forall \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{R}_2, \sigma_3$.

$(\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma_3(\Phi, \Phi_3); \mathcal{R}_2 \vdash \sigma_3 \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}', \mathcal{C}_3; \mathcal{L}', \mathcal{L}_3; \mathcal{R}'_2, \mathcal{R}_3)) \Rightarrow$

$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma(\Phi, \Phi_3); \mathcal{R}_2 \vdash \sigma(texpr) \Leftarrow \sigma(ret_2)$.

PROOF: By induction on (2)1.

(2)3. σ and \mathcal{R} can be split up into σ_1 and $\mathcal{R}_1; \sigma_2$; and σ_3 and \mathcal{R}_2 such that:

1. $\mathcal{R} = \mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2$

2. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma(\Phi); \mathcal{R}_1 \vdash \sigma_1 \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \mathcal{R}'_1)$

3. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma(\Phi); \cdot \vdash \sigma_2 \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \cdot)$

4. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma(\Phi); \mathcal{R}_2 \vdash \sigma_3 \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \mathcal{R}'_2)$.

PROOF: By lemma B7.2 (Substitutions can be split up).

- ⟨2⟩4. 1. $\sigma(\Phi) = \sigma_1(\Phi) = \sigma_2(\Phi) = \sigma_3(\Phi)$
 2. $\sigma(\Phi_3) = \sigma_2(\Phi_3) = \sigma_3(\Phi_3)$
 3. $\sigma(\mathcal{R}_3) = \sigma_2(\mathcal{R}_3) = \sigma_3(\mathcal{R}_3)$.

PROOF: All the substitutions differ only the resource-variable substitutions, but *term* and *res* (and so *ret* and Φ) do not mention resource variables.

- ⟨2⟩5. SUFFICES: $\exists \mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2, ret_1, \mathcal{C}_3, \mathcal{L}_3, \Phi_3, \mathcal{R}_3$.

1. $\mathcal{R} = \mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2$
2. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma(\Phi); \mathcal{R}_1 \vdash \sigma(seq_expr) \Rightarrow ret_1$
3. $\sigma(\Phi) \vdash ret_pat: \sigma(ret_1) \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_3; \mathcal{L}_3; \Phi_3; \mathcal{R}_3$
4. $\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_3; \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{L}_3; \sigma(\Phi), \Phi_3; \mathcal{R}_2, \mathcal{R}_3 \vdash \sigma(texpr) \Leftarrow \sigma(ret_2)$.

PROOF: By EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LET.

- ⟨2⟩6. LET: $\mathcal{R}_1; \mathcal{R}_2; \sigma(ret_1); \mathcal{C}_3; \mathcal{L}_3; \sigma(\Phi_3); \sigma(\mathcal{R}_3)$ be the witnesses for ⟨2⟩5.

- SUFFICES: 1. $\mathcal{R} = \mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2$
 2. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma(\Phi); \mathcal{R}_1 \vdash \sigma(seq_expr) \Rightarrow \sigma(ret_1)$
 3. $\sigma(\Phi) \vdash ret_pat: \sigma(ret_1) \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_3; \mathcal{L}_3; \sigma(\Phi_3); \sigma(\mathcal{R}_3)$
 4. $\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_3; \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{L}_3; \sigma(\Phi), \sigma(\Phi_3); \mathcal{R}_2, \sigma(\mathcal{R}_3) \vdash \sigma(texpr) \Leftarrow \sigma(ret_2)$.

- ⟨2⟩7. We are done.

PROOF: Apply ⟨2⟩2 with ⟨2⟩3 and ⟨2⟩4.

- ⟨1⟩6. CASE: All remaining rules.

PROOF SKETCH: By straightforward induction. If the rule has a **smt** ($\Phi \Rightarrow qterm$) premise, apply lemma B7.1 (Substitutions preserve SMT results).

B8 Resource Term Lemmas

B8.1 Definition: Normalised contexts

A resource context is *normalised* if it contains only predicates, quantified predicates and under-determined conditional resources.

B8.2 Resource contexts typing closed terms must be normalised

ASSUME: 1. Arbitrary res
2. Closed (no free-variables) res_term
3. $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash res_term \Leftarrow res$ (or synthesising)

PROVE: $\exists \underline{\mathcal{R}}. \mathcal{R} = \underline{\mathcal{R}}$.

PROOF SKETCH: By induction on the typing judgement.

(1)1. CASE: RES_SYN_EMP, RES_SYN_PRED, RES_SYN_QPRED, RES_CHK_PHI.
PROOF: $\underline{\mathcal{R}} = \mathcal{R}$ (the context is already normalised).

(1)2. CASE: RES_SYN_VAR, RES_SYN_VARSIMP
PROOF: Impossible cases (res_terms are not closed).

(1)3. CASE: All remaining cases (RES_SYN_PREDOPS_ITERATE, RES_SYN_PREDOPS_CONGEAL, RES_SYN_PREDOPS_EXPLODE, RES_SYN_PREDOPS_IMPLODE, RES_SYN_PREDOPS_BREAK, RES_SYN_PREDOPS_GLUE, RES_SYN_PREDOPS_INJ, RES_SYN_PREDOPS_SPLIT, RES_SYN_PREDOPS, RES_SYN_FOLD, RES_SYN_SEPCONJ, RES_CHK_PACK, RES_CHK_SEPCONJ, RES_CHK_IF_TRUE, RES_CHK_IF_FALSE, RES_CHK_SWITCH).
PROOF: By induction.

B8.3 Non-conditional resources determine context and values

This is a simple inversion lemma.

ASSUME: 1. Arbitrary res_val
2. $res \neq \mathbf{if\ term\ then\ } res_1 \mathbf{\ else\ } res_2$.
3. $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash res_val \Leftarrow res$ (or synthesising)

(1)1. The typing assumption cannot be any of: RES_SYN_VAR, RES_SYN_VARSIMP, RES_SYN_FOLD, RES_SYN_PREDOPS_ITERATE, RES_SYN_PREDOPS_CONGEAL, RES_SYN_PREDOPS_EXPLODE, RES_SYN_PREDOPS_IMPLODE, RES_SYN_PREDOPS_BREAK, RES_SYN_PREDOPS_GLUE, RES_SYN_PREDOPS_INJ, RES_SYN_PREDOPS_SPLIT, RES_SYN_PREDOPS.
PROOF: res_terms in these rules are not values.

(1)2. If $res = \mathbf{emp}$, then $\underline{\mathcal{R}} = \cdot$ and $res_val = \mathbf{emp}$.
PROOF: By inversion, the assumption must be RES_SYN_EMP (and optionally RES_CHK_

SWITCH).

- (1)3. If $res = term$, then $\underline{\mathcal{R}} = \cdot$ and $res_val = \mathbf{term}$.
 PROOF: By inversion, the assumption must be RES_CHK_PHI.
- (1)4. If $res = pred_term(oarg)$, then $\underline{\mathcal{R}} = _ : pred_term(oarg)$ and $res_val = pred_term$.
 PROOF: By inversion, the assumption must be RES_SYN_PRED (and optionally RES_CHK_SWITCH).
- (1)5. If $res = qpred_term(oarg)$, then $\underline{\mathcal{R}} = _ : qpred_term(oarg)$ and $res_val = qpred_term$.
 PROOF: By inversion, the assumption must be RES_SYN_QPRED (and optionally RES_CHK_SWITCH).
- (1)6. If $res = res_1 * res_2$, then $\underline{\mathcal{R}} = \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2$ and $res_val = \langle res_val_1, res_val_2 \rangle$.
 PROOF: By inversion, the assumption must be RES_SYN_SEPCONJ (and optionally RES_CHK_SWITCH), or RES_CHK_SEPCONJ.
- (1)7. If $res = \exists y:\beta. res$, then $res_val = \mathbf{pack}(oarg, res_val')$.
 PROOF: By inversion, the assumption must be RES_CHK_PACK.

B8.4 Normalised resource context determines structure of heap

This is as simple inversion lemma.

ASSUME: $\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}$.

- (1)1. If $\underline{\mathcal{R}} = \cdot$, then $h = \cdot$.
 PROOF: By inversion, the assumption must be HEAP_EMPTY.
- (1)2. If $pred = ptr \xrightarrow{\tau}^{init} value$, $\underline{\mathcal{R}} = _ : pred$, then $h = \{pred' \ \& \ \mathbf{None}\}$ for $\Phi \vdash pred \equiv pred'$.
 PROOF: By inversion, the assumption must be HEAP_PRED_OWNED.
- (1)3. If $\underline{\mathcal{R}} = _ : pred$, then $h = \{pred' \ \& \ def \ \& \ h'\}$.
 for $\Phi \vdash pred \equiv pred'$.
 PROOF: By inversion, the assumption must be HEAP_PRED_OTHER.
- (1)4. If $qpred = * x. iguard \Rightarrow ptr + x \times \text{size_of}(\tau) \xrightarrow{\tau}^{oarg[x].init} oarg[x].value$, $\underline{\mathcal{R}} = _ : qpred$, then $h = \{qpred' \ \& \ \cdot\}$ for $\Phi \vdash qpred \equiv qpred'$.
 PROOF: By inversion, the assumption must be HEAP_QPRED_OWNED.
- (1)5. If $\underline{\mathcal{R}} = _ : qpred$, then $h = \{qpred' \ \& \ arr_def_heap\}$ for $\Phi \vdash qpred \equiv qpred'$.
 PROOF: By inversion, the assumption must be HEAP_QPRED_OTHER.
- (1)6. If $\underline{\mathcal{R}} = \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2$, then $h = h_1 + h_2$, where $\Phi \vdash h_1 \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1$ and $\Phi \vdash h_2 \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2$.
 PROOF: By inversion, the assumption must be HEAP_CONCAT.

B8.5 Well-typed resource value determines its footprint

ASSUME: $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash res_val \Leftarrow res$ (or synthesising)
 $\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}$.

PROVE: $\forall f. footprint_of\ res_val\ in\ h + f \rightsquigarrow h\ rem\ f$.

PROOF SKETCH: By induction on the typing judgement.

(1)1. CASE: RES_SYN_EMP or RES_CHK_PHI

$\underline{\mathcal{R}} = \cdot$ and so $h = \cdot$ by lemma B8.4.

PROOF: FOOTPRINT_EMP or FOOTPRINT_TERM respectively.

(1)2. CASE: RES_SYN_PRED or RES_SYN_QPRED

$\underline{\mathcal{R}} = \cdot; pred_term(oarg)$ or $\cdot; qpred_term(oarg)$, and so

$h = \{pred_term(oarg) \ \& \ opt_def_heap\}$ or $\{qpred_term(oarg) \ \& \ arr_def_heap\}$ by lemma B8.4.

PROOF: FOOTPRINT_PRED or FOOTPRINT_QPRED respectively.

(1)3. CASE: pack($oarg, res_val'$).

PROOF: By induction.

(1)4. CASE: FOOTPRINT_SEPAIR.

$res_val = \langle res_val_1, res_val_2 \rangle$,

$\underline{\mathcal{R}} = \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2$, and so

$h = h_1 + h_2$ where $\Phi \vdash h_1 \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1$ and $\Phi \vdash h_2 \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2$ by lemma B8.4.

(2)1. footprint_of res_val_1 in $h_1 + h_2 + f \rightsquigarrow h_1\ rem\ h_2 + f$.

PROOF: Instantiate inductive hypothesis with $h_2 + f$.

(2)2. footprint_of res_val_1 in $h_2 + f \rightsquigarrow h_2\ rem\ f$.

PROOF: Instantiate inductive hypothesis with f .

B8.6 Progress and type preservation for resource terms

ASSUME: 1. Closed (no free-variables) res_term
 2. $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash res_term \Leftarrow res$ (or synthesising)
 3. $\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}$

PROVE: $\exists res_val, \underline{\mathcal{R}}', h'$.

1. $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash res_val \Leftarrow res$ (or synthesising respectively)

2. $\Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$

3. $\forall f. \langle h + f; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + f; res_val \rangle$.

PROOF SKETCH: Induction on the resource term typing assumption. The type dictates the value and context, the latter of which dictates the shape of the heap.

Because of this direction of information, you cannot prove that

$\forall \mathcal{R}'. (\Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \mathcal{R}') \Rightarrow (\cdot; \cdot; \cdot; \mathcal{R}'' \vdash res_val' \Leftarrow res)$. The converse is already true by the composition of lemmas B8.3 and B8.4. You need the existential, so that you can provide it as a witness when proving heap typing for folded predicates, which you need to use in proving unfolding predicates in pattern-matching.

(1)1. CASE: RES_SYN_PREDOPS_ITERATE

LET: $res_term = \text{iterate}(res_term', n)$
 $qpred_term = (x; 0 \leq x \wedge x \leq n - 1) \{ \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (ptr + x \times \text{size_of}(\tau)) \}$
 $res = qpred_term(oarg)$
 $pred_term = \text{Owned} \langle \text{array } n \tau \rangle (ptr)$
 $res' = pred_term(oarg')$.

(2)1. $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash res_term' \Rightarrow res'$.

PROOF: By inversion on the typing assumption.

(2)2. $\exists h'', \mathcal{R}'', res_val'$.

1. $\cdot; \cdot; \cdot; \mathcal{R}'' \vdash res_val' \Rightarrow res'$

2. $\Phi \vdash h'' \Leftarrow \mathcal{R}''$

3. $\forall f. \langle h + f; res_term' \rangle \Downarrow \langle h'' + f; res_val' \rangle$.

PROOF: By the induction hypothesis.

(2)3. $res_val' = pred_term$ and $\mathcal{R}'' = \cdot; res'$.

PROOF: By (2)2 and lemma B8.3 (Non-conditional resources determine context and values).

(2)4. $h'' = \{ pred_term(oarg') \ \& \ \text{None} \}$.

PROOF: By (2)3 and lemma B8.4 (Normalised resource context determines structure of heap).

(2)5. LET: $res_val = (x; 0 \leq x \wedge x \leq n - 1) \{ \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (ptr + x \times \text{size_of}(\tau)) \}$

$\mathcal{R}' = \cdot; qpred_term(oarg)$ and $h' = \{ qpred_term(oarg) \ \& \ \cdot \}$.

PROOF: Prove value typing using RES_SYN_QPRED; heaping typing using HEAP_QPRED_OWNED; reduction using PREDOPS_RESV_ITERATE.

(1)2. CASE: RES_SYN_PREDOPS_CONGEAL

PROOF: Like RES_SYN_PREDOPS_ITERATE, but with:

$res_term = \text{congeal}(res_term', n)$

$res = pred_term(oarg)$ where $pred_term = \text{Owned} \langle \text{array } n \tau \rangle (ptr)$

$res' = qpred_term(oarg')$ where $qpred_term = (x; iguard) \{ \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (ptr + x \times \text{size_of}(\tau)) \}$

$res_val' = qpred_term$ and $\mathcal{R}'' = \cdot; res'$, by lemma B8.3

Let $res_val = pred_term$, $\mathcal{R}' = \cdot; pred_term(oarg)$ and $h' = \{ pred_term(oarg) \ \& \ \text{None} \}$ to

prove: value typing using RES_SYN_PRED; heap typing using HEAP_PRED_OWNED;

reduction using PREDOPS_RESV_CONGEAL.

(1)3. CASE: RES_SYN_PREDOPS_EXPLODE

PROOF: Like RES_SYN_PREDOPS_ITERATE, but with:

$res_term = \text{explode}(res_term')$

$res = * (\overline{pred_term_i(oarg_i)^i})$ where $pred_term_i = \mathbf{Owned} \langle \tau_i \rangle (ptr +_{\text{ptr}} \text{offset_of}_{tag}(member_i))$

$res' = pred_term(oarg)$ where $pred_term = \mathbf{Owned} \langle \text{struct } tag \rangle (ptr)$
 $res_val' = pred_term$ and $\underline{\mathcal{R}}'' = _ : pred_term(oarg)$, by lemma B8.3

Let $res_val = \langle \overline{pred_term_i^i} \rangle$, $\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = _ : \overline{pred_term_i(oarg_i)^i}$ and
 $h' = \overline{\{pred_term_i(oarg_i) \& \text{None}\}^i}$, to prove: value typing using RES_SYN_PRED and RES_SYN_SEPCONJ; heap typing using HEAP_CONCAT and HEAP_PRED_OWNED; reduction using PREDOPS_RESV_EXPLODE.

(1)4. CASE: RES_SYN_PREDOPS_IMPLODE

PROOF: Like RES_SYN_PREDOPS_ITERATE, but with:

$res_term = \mathbf{implode}(res_term', tag)$

$res = pred_term(oarg)$ where $pred_term = \mathbf{Owned} \langle \text{struct } tag \rangle (ptr)$

$res' = * (\overline{pred_term_i(oarg_i)^i})$ where $pred_term_i = \mathbf{Owned} \langle \tau_i \rangle (ptr +_{\text{ptr}} \text{offset_of}_{tag}(member_i))$
 $res_val' = \overline{pred_term_i^i}$ and $\underline{\mathcal{R}}'' = _ : \overline{pred_term_i(oarg_i)^i}$, by lemma B8.3

Let $res_val = \mathbf{Owned} \langle \text{struct } tag \rangle (ptr)$, $\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = _ : pred_term(oarg)$, and
 $h' = \{pred_term(oarg) \& \text{None}\}$, to prove: value typing using RES_SYN_PRED; heap typing using HEAP_PRED_OWNED; reduction using PREDOPS_RESV_IMPLODE.

(1)5. CASE: RES_SYN_PREDOPS_BREAK

PROOF: Like RES_SYN_PREDOPS_ITERATE, but with:

$res_term = \mathbf{break}(res_term', term)$

$res = qpred_term(oarg) * pred_term(oarg[term])$ where

$qpred_term = (x; iguard \wedge (x \neq term)) \{ \alpha(ptr + x \times step, iargs) \}$ and

$pred_term = \alpha(ptr + (term \times step), term/x(iargs))$

$res' = qpred_term'(oarg)$ where $qpred_term' = (x; iguard) \{ \alpha(ptr + x \times step, iargs) \}$
 $res_val' = qpred_term'$, and $\underline{\mathcal{R}}'' = _ : qpred_term'(oarg)$, by lemma B8.3.

If predicate is $\mathbf{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle$, $h'' = \{qpred_term'(oarg) \& \cdot\}$ (by lemma B8.4), so let
 $h' = \{qpred_term(oarg) \& \cdot\} + \{pred_term(oarg[term]) \& \text{None}\}$ (by $\cdot[term] = \text{None}$).
 Otherwise, $h'' = \{qpred_term'(oarg) \& arr_def_heap\}$, (again by lemma B8.4), so let
 $h' = \{qpred_term(oarg) \& arr_def_heap\} + \{pred_term(oarg[term]) \& arr_def_heap[term]\}$.

Let $res_val = \langle qpred_term, pred_term \rangle$ and

$\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = _ : qpred_term(oarg), _ : pred_term(oarg[term])$ to prove: value typing using RES_SYN_QPRED, RES_SYN_PRED, RES_SYN_SEPCONJ; heap typing using HEAP_CONCAT, HEAP_QPRED_OWNED / HEAP_QPRED_OTHER, and HEAP_PRED_OWNED / HEAP_PRED_OTHER (with witness $_ : pred_term(oarg[term])$); reduction using PREDOPS_RESV_BREAK.

(1)6. CASE: RES_SYN_PREDOPS_GLUE

PROOF: Like RES_SYN_PREDOPS_ITERATE, but with:

$res_term = \mathbf{glue}(res_term')$

$res = qpred_term(oarg_1[term] := oarg_2)$ where
 $qpred_term = (x; iguard \vee x = term)\{\alpha(ptr_1 + x \times step, \overline{iarg_1}_i^i)\}$

$res' = qpred_term_1(oarg_1) * pred_term(oarg_2)$ where
 $qpred_term_1 = (x; iguard)\{\alpha(ptr_1 + x \times step, \overline{iarg_1}_i^i)\}$ and $pred_term = \alpha(ptr_2, \overline{iarg_2}_i^i)$.
 $res_val' = \langle qpred_term_1, pred_term \rangle$, and $\underline{\mathcal{R}}'' = \vdash : qpred_term_1(oarg_1), \vdash : pred_term(oarg_2)$, by lemma B8.3.

If predicate is **Owned** $\langle \tau \rangle$, $h'' = \{qpred_term_1(oarg_1) \& \cdot\} + \{pred_term(oarg_2) \& \text{None}\}$ (by lemma B8.4), so let $h' = \{qpred_term(oarg) \& \cdot\}$ (by $\cdot[term] := \text{None} = \cdot$). Otherwise, $h'' = \{qpred_term_1(oarg_1) \& arr_def_heap\} + \{pred_term(oarg_2) \& def \& heap\}$ (again by lemma B8.4), so let $h' = \{qpred_term(oarg) \& arr_def_heap[term] := def \& heap\}$.

Let $res_val = qpred_term$ and $\underline{\mathcal{R}} = \vdash : qpred_term(oarg_1[term] := oarg_2)$, to prove: value typing using RES_SYN_QPRED; heap typing using HEAP_QPRED_OWNED / HEAP_QPRED_OTHER; reduction using PREDOPS_RESV_GLUE.

(1)7. CASE: RES_SYN_PREDOPS_INJ

PROOF: Like RES_SYN_PREDOPS_ITERATE, but with:
 $res_term = inj(res_term', ptr_1, step, x. \overline{iarg_1}_i^i)$
 $res = qpred_term((\text{default array } \beta)[term] := oarg)$ where
 $qpred_term = (x; x = term)\{\alpha(ptr_1 + x \times step, \overline{iarg_1}_i^i)\}$

$res' = pred_term(oarg)$ where $pred_term = \alpha(ptr_2, \overline{iarg_2}_i^i)$
 $res_val' = pred_term$, and $\underline{\mathcal{R}}'' = \vdash : pred_term(oarg)$, by lemma B8.3.

If predicate is **Owned** $\langle \tau \rangle$, $h'' = \{pred_term(oarg) \& \text{None}\}$ (by lemma B8.4), so let $h' = \{qpred_term((\text{default array } \beta)[term] := oarg) \& \cdot\}$ (by $\cdot[term] := \text{None} = \cdot$). Otherwise, $h'' = \{pred_term(oarg) \& def \& heap\}$ (again by lemma B8.4), so let $h' = \{qpred_term((\text{default array } \beta)[term] := oarg) \& \cdot[term] := def \& heap\}$.

Let $res_val = qpred_term$, and $\underline{\mathcal{R}} = \vdash : qpred_term((\text{default array } \beta)[term] := oarg)$, to prove typing using HEAP_QPRED_OWNED / HEAP_QPRED_OTHER, and reduction using PREDOPS_RESV_INJ.

(1)8. CASE: RES_SYN_PREDOPS_SPLIT

PROOF: Like RES_SYN_PREDOPS_ITERATE, but with:
 $res_term = split(res_term', iguard)$
 $res = qpred_term_1(oarg) * qpred_term_2(oarg)$ where
 $qpred_term_1 = (x; iguard)\{\alpha(ptr + x \times step, iargs)\}$ and
 $qpred_term_2 = (x; iguard_2)\{\alpha(ptr + x \times step, iargs)\}$

$res' = qpred_term(oarg)$ where $qpred_term = (x; iguard')\{\alpha(ptr + x \times step, iargs)\}$
 $res_val' = qpred_term$, and $\underline{\mathcal{R}}'' = \vdash : qpred_term(oarg)$, by lemma B8.3.

If predicate is **Owned** $\langle \tau \rangle$, $h'' = \{qpred_term(oarg) \& \cdot\}$ (by lemma B8.4), so let $h' = \{qpred_term_1(oarg) \& \cdot\} + \{qpred_term_2(oarg) \& \cdot\}$. Otherwise,

$h'' = \{qpred_term(oarg) \& arr_def_heap\}$ (again by lemma B8.4), so let
 $h' = \{qpred_term_1(oarg) \& arr_def_heap\} + \{qpred_term_2(oarg) \& arr_def_heap\}$.

Let $res_val = \langle qpred_term_1, qpred_term_2 \rangle$, and
 $\underline{\mathcal{R}} = \cdot : qpred_term_1(oarg), \cdot : qpred_term_2(oarg)$, to prove: value typing using RES_SYN_QPRED and RES_SYN_SEPCONJ; heap typing using HEAP_CONCAT and HEAP_QPRED_OWNED / HEAP_QPRED_OTHER; reduction using PREDOPS_RESV_SPLIT.

(1)9. CASE: RES_SYN_EMP, RES_SYN_PRED, RES_SYN_QPRED, RES_CHK_PHI.

PROOF: In these cases, $h = h'$, $\underline{\mathcal{R}} = \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$ and $res_term = res_val$.

Typing holds by assumption; prove reduction using REST_RESV_VAL.

(1)10. CASE: RES_SYN_PREDOPS

PROOF: Both typing and reduction (using REST_RESV_PREDOPS) hold by induction.

(1)11. CASE: RES_SYN_SEPCONJ, RES_CHK_SEPCONJ.

$res = res_1 * res_2$,

$res_term = \langle res_term_1, res_term_2 \rangle$,

$h = h_1 + h_2$, so $\underline{\mathcal{R}} = \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2$,

$\Phi \vdash h_1 \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1$ and $\Phi \vdash h_2 \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2$.

(2)1. $\exists h'_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1, res_val_1 \dots \wedge (\forall f_1 \dots)$

$\exists h'_2, \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_2, res_val_2 \dots \wedge (\forall f_2 \dots)$

PROOF: By induction.

(2)2. $\langle h_1 + h_2 + f; res_term_1 \rangle \Downarrow \langle h'_1 + h_2 + f; res_val_1 \rangle$.

$\langle h'_1 + h_2 + f; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h'_1 + h'_2 + f; res_val_2 \rangle$.

PROOF: Instantiate f_1 with $h_2 + f$, and f_2 with, $h'_1 + f$.

(2)3. LET: $res_val = \langle res_val_1, res_val_2 \rangle$, $\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_2$, and $h' = h'_1 + h'_2$.

Prove value typing using RES_SYN_SEPCONJ / RES_CHK_SEPCONJ; heap typing using HEAP_CONCAT; reduction using (2)2 and REST_RESV_SEPPAIR.

(1)12. CASE: RES_CHK_PACK

PROOF: Like RES_SYN_PREDOPS_ITERATE, but with:

$res_term = \mathbf{pack}(oarg, res_term')$, $res = \exists y:\beta. res''$, $res' = oarg/y(res'')$

$res_val = \mathbf{pack}(oarg, res_val')$. Value and heap typing hold by induction; prove reduction using REST_RESV_PACK.

(1)13. CASE: RES_SYN_FOLD

PROOF: Like RES_SYN_PREDOPS_ITERATE, but with:

$\alpha \equiv x_p : -, \overline{x_i} : -^i, y : - \mapsto res'' \in \mathbf{Globals}$

$res_term = \mathbf{fold} res_term' : \alpha(ptr, \overline{iarg}_i^i)(oarg)$

$res = \alpha(ptr, \overline{iarg}_i^i)(oarg)$

$res' = [oarg/y, [\overline{iarg}_i/x_i^i], ptr/x_p](res'')$.

$\exists h_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}', res_val'$.

1. $\cdot ; \cdot ; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash res_val' \Leftarrow res'$

2. $\Phi \vdash h_1 \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$
 3. $\forall f. \langle h + f; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h_1 + f; res_val' \rangle$
- (by induction).

Let $res_val = \alpha(ptr, \overline{iarg}_i^i)$, $\underline{\mathcal{R}'} = \lambda oarg. \alpha(ptr, \overline{iarg}_i^i)(oarg)$ and $h' = \{\alpha(ptr, \overline{iarg}_i^i)(oarg) \& res_val' \& h_1\}$, to prove: value typing using RES_SYN_PRED; heap typing using HEAP_PRED_OTHER.
 Since **footprint of res_val' in $h_1 + f \rightsquigarrow h_1 \text{ rem } f$** by lemma B8.5 (**Well-typed resource value determines its footprint**), prove reduction using REST_RESV_FOLD.

- (1)14. CASE: RES_CHK_IF_TRUE, RES_CHK_IF_FALSE
 PROOF: By induction with res' as res_1 or res_2 respectively. This is exhaustive because only variables can synthesise under-determined conditional resources and those are excluded by assumption of res_term being closed.
- (1)15. CASE: RES_CHK_SWITCH
 PROOF: By induction on the synthesising judgement.

B8.7 Resource term reduction is deterministic

PROOF SKETCH: Induction over the definition: it is syntax directed.

B8.8 Resource term reduction is isolated

If res_term is closed, $(\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash res_term \Leftarrow res) \wedge (\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}})$ and $\langle h + f; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle heap; res_val \rangle$ then $\exists h', \underline{\mathcal{R}'}. heap = h' + f \wedge (\Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}'}) \wedge (\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}'} \vdash res_val \Leftarrow res)$.

PROOF: This simply the composition of lemma B8.7 (**Resource term reduction is deterministic**) and lemma B8.6 (**Progress and type preservation for resource terms**).

B9 Progress

B9.1 $\Phi \vdash res \sim res'$ is an equivalence relation

PROOF SKETCH: By induction and $term \sim term'$ assumed to be an equivalence relation (see section B4 Proof Judgements).

B9.2 $\Phi \vdash res \sim res'$ is preserved by substitution

If $x \sim y$ in $\Phi \vdash res \sim res'$ and $term \sim term'$ then $\Phi \vdash term/x(res) \sim term/y(res')$.

PROOF SKETCH: By induction and $term \sim term'$ assumed to be preserved by substitution (see section B4 Proof Judgements).

B9.3 Well-typed spines produce substitutions and the same return type

ASSUME: $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \overline{spine_elem_i^i} :: \psi_1(fun_1) \gg ret_1$
 $\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}$ and $\psi_1(fun_1) = \psi_2(fun_2) = \psi_2(fun_3)$
 $\langle h + f; x_i = \overline{spine_elem_i^i} \rangle :: \psi_2(fun_2) \gg \langle heap; \sigma_2; ret_2 \rangle$
 $\overline{x_i^i} :: fun_3 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}' \mid ret_3$.

PROVE: $\psi_1(ret_1) = \psi_2(ret_2) = [\psi_2, \sigma_2](ret_3)$
 $\exists h', \underline{\mathcal{R}}'. heap = h' + f, \Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ and
 $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \psi_2(\sigma_2) \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \psi_2(\mathcal{R}'))$.

(1)1. CASE: EXPL_SPINE_RET

$\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \psi_1(ret_1) \gg \psi_1(ret)$
 $\Phi \vdash \cdot \Leftarrow \cdot$ (by inversion, HEAP_EMPTY).
 $\langle f; \cdot \rangle :: \psi_2(ret) \gg \langle f; \cdot; \psi_2(ret) \rangle$ (by inversion, SUBS_SPINE_EMPTY).
 $:: ret \rightsquigarrow \cdot; \cdot; \cdot \mid ret$ where $ret'' = ret$ (by inversion, FUN_ENV_RET).

$\psi_1(ret_1) = \psi_2(ret_2) = [\psi_2, \cdot](ret_3)$ (by assumption)

LET: $h' = \cdot, \underline{\mathcal{R}}' = \cdot$.

$f = h' + f$ trivially.

$\Phi \vdash \cdot \Leftarrow \cdot$ by HEAP_EMPTY.

$\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \cdot \Leftarrow (\cdot; \cdot; \cdot)$ by SUBS_CHK_EMPTY.

(1)2. CASE: EXPL_SPINE_COMP

$\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \overline{spine_elem_i^i} :: [pval/x, \psi_1](fun'_1) \gg ret_1$
 $\cdot \vdash pval \Rightarrow \beta$
 $\langle h + f; x_i = \overline{spine_elem_i^i} \rangle :: [pval/x, \psi_2](fun'_2) \gg \langle heap; \sigma'_2; ret_2 \rangle$
 (by inversion, SUBS_SPINE_COMP) $x, \overline{x_i^i} :: \Pi x:\beta. fun'_3 \rightsquigarrow x:\beta, \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}' \mid ret_3$ (by inversion, FUN_ENV_COMP).

$[pval/x, \psi_1](ret_1) = [pval/x, \psi_2](ret_2) = [pval/x, \psi_2, \sigma'_2](ret_3)$

$\exists h', \underline{\mathcal{R}}'. heap = h' + f, \Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ and

$\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash [pval/x, \psi_2](\sigma'_2) \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}; [pval/x, \psi_2](\mathcal{R}'))$ (by induction).

$[\psi_2, pval/x, \sigma'_2](ret_3) = [pval/x, \psi_2, \sigma'_2]$ and
 $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \psi_2([pval/x, \sigma'_2]) \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}', x; \beta; \mathcal{L}; \psi_2(\underline{\mathcal{R}}'))$,
 by SUBS_CHK_COMP and SUBS_CHK_CONCAT (because $pval$ is closed, we have
 $[pval/x, \psi_2(\sigma'_2)] = \psi_2([pval/x, \sigma'_2])$).

(1)3. CASE: EXPL_SPINE_COMP

Similar to EXPL_SPINE_COMP but with SUBS_CHK_LOG.

(1)4. CASE: EXPL_SPINE_PHI

By induction (does not affect substitution).

(1)5. CASE: EXPL_SPINE_RES

$\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2 \vdash \overline{spine_elem_i}^i :: \psi_1(fun_1) \gg ret_1$

$\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1 \vdash res_term \Leftarrow \psi_1(res)$

$\exists h_1, h_2. h = h_1 + h_2 \wedge \Phi \vdash h_1 \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1 \wedge \Phi \vdash h_2 \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2$ (by B8.4).

$\langle h_1 + h_2 + f; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle heap_1; res_val \rangle$

$\langle heap_1; \overline{spine_elem_i}^i \rangle :: [res_val/x, \psi'_2](fun_2) \gg \langle heap_2; \sigma'_2; ret_2 \rangle$ (by inversion, SUBS_SPINE_RES).

$\exists h'_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1, res_val'. \cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1 \vdash res_val' \Leftarrow \psi_1(res), \Phi \vdash h'_1 \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1$

and $\langle h_1 + h_2 + f; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h'_1 + h_2 + f; res_val' \rangle$

(by lemma B8.6 (Progress and type preservation for resource terms)).

$heap_1 = h'_1 + h_2 + f$ and $res_val = res_val'$

(by lemma B8.8 (Resource term reduction is isolated))

$\psi_1(ret_1) = [res_val/x, \psi_2](ret_2) = [res_val/x, \psi_2, \sigma'_2](ret_3)$

(because resources variables not in types)

$\exists h'_2, \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_2. heap_2 = h'_2 + h'_1 + f \wedge \Phi \vdash h'_2 \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_2$

$\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_2 \vdash [res_val/x, \psi_2](\sigma'_2) \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; [res_val/x, \psi_2](\underline{\mathcal{R}}'))$ (by induction).

LET: $h' = h'_1 + h'_2$ and $\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_2$.

Hence $\Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_2$ (by HEAP_CONCAT),

$[res_val/x, \psi_2, \sigma'_2](ret_3) = [\psi_2, res_val/x, \sigma'_2](ret_3)$ and

$\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_2 \vdash \psi_2([res_val/x, \sigma'_2]) \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \psi_2(x; res, \underline{\mathcal{R}}'))$, by SUBS_CHK_RES and SUBS_

CHK_CONCAT (because res_val is closed, we have $[res_val/x, \psi_2(\sigma'_2)] = \psi_2([res_val/x, \sigma'_2])$).

B9.4 Well-typed values pattern-match successfully

Note that the definition of $term \sim term'$ is not explicitly stated; see section B4 (Proof Judgements) for more details.

- ASSUME: 1. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \overline{ret_pat_i}^i : ret \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$
 2. $\overline{ret_pat_i}^i$ is exhaustive
 3. $\Phi \vdash fun \sim ret$
 4. $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \overline{ret_term_i}^i :: fun \gg \mathbf{I}$
 5. $\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}$

PROVE: $\exists h', \sigma.$
 $\forall f. \langle h + f; \overline{ret_pat}_i = \overline{ret_term}_i^i \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h' + f; \sigma \rangle$
 $\exists \underline{\mathcal{R}}'.$
 $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \wedge \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \sigma \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \mathcal{R}').$

PROOF SKETCH: Induction over the pattern-matching judgement.

(1)1. CASE: PAT_RET_EMPTY

$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash :I \rightsquigarrow ; ; ; \cdot$
 which means $fun = I$ (by inversion, REL_RET_I)
 and so $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash :I \gg I$ (by inversion, EXPL_SPINE_RET),
 and $h = \cdot$ (by lemma B8.4).
 Let $h' = \cdot$, to step with SUBS_PAT_RET_EMPTY.
 Let $\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = \cdot$, to type h' with HEAP_EMPTY and σ with SUBS_CHK_EMPTY.

(1)2. CASE: PAT_RET_COMP

$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{comp_ident_or_pat}, \overline{ret_pat}_j^j : \Sigma y : \beta. ret \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2; \mathcal{L}_2; \Phi_2; \mathcal{R}_2$
 which means $fun = \Pi x : \beta. fun'$ (by inversion, REL_RET_COMP),
 and so $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash pval, \overline{ret_term}_j^j :: \Pi x : \beta. fun' \gg I$ (by inversion, EXPL_SPINE_COMP).

$ident_or_pat : \beta \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_1$ with $term_1$ (from the pattern-matching assumption),
 $ident_or_pat$ is exhaustive (from the exhaustive assumption),
 and $\cdot \vdash pval \Rightarrow \beta$ (from the spine typing assumption),
 imply $term_1 \sim pval$, $ident_or_pat = pval \rightsquigarrow \sigma_1$
 and $; ; ; \cdot \vdash \sigma_1 \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}_1; ; \cdot)$ (by the nested proof below).

$\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \overline{ret_pat}_j^j : term_1 / y(ret') \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_2; \mathcal{L}_2; \Phi_2; \mathcal{R}_2$ (from the pattern-matching assumption),
 $\forall term_1 \sim pval. \Phi \vdash pval / x(fun') \sim term_1 / y(ret')$ (from the related assumption),
 $; ; ; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \overline{ret_term}_j^j :: pval / x(fun') \gg I$ (from the spine typing assumption),
 and $\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}$, imply $\langle h + f; \overline{ret_pat}_j = \overline{ret_term}_j^j \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h'' + f; \sigma_2 \rangle$
 and that $\exists \underline{\mathcal{R}}''$ such that $\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash h'' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}''$ and $\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}'' \vdash \sigma_2 \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}_2; \mathcal{L}_2; \mathcal{R}_2)$ (by induction).

Since $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \sigma_1(\Phi); \sigma_1(\underline{\mathcal{R}}') \vdash [id, \sigma_1] \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}; \underline{\mathcal{R}}')$, and $\sigma_1(\Phi) = \Phi$ (because Φ is well-scoped / does not contain any variables from \mathcal{C}_1) we have $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \sigma_1(h'') \Leftarrow \sigma_1(\underline{\mathcal{R}}'')$ and $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \sigma_1(\underline{\mathcal{R}}') \vdash \sigma_1(\sigma_2) \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}_2; \mathcal{L}_2; \sigma_1(\mathcal{R}_2))$ (by lemma B7.3 (Substitution)).

LET: $h' = \sigma_1(h'')$, $\sigma = [\sigma_1, \sigma_2]$ to step with SUBS_PAT_RET_COMP.
 $\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = \sigma_1(\underline{\mathcal{R}}'')$.

So $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$
 and $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \sigma \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2; \mathcal{L}_2; \mathcal{R}_2)$ hold by lemma B6 (Weakening) and SUBS_CHK_CONCAT.

ASSUME: 1. $ident_or_pat : \beta \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_1$ with $term_1$

2. $ident_or_pat$ is exhaustive

3. $\cdot \vdash pval \Rightarrow \beta$

PROVE: 1. $term_1 \sim pval$

2. $\exists \sigma. ident_or_pat = pval \rightsquigarrow \sigma$ and $\cdot; \cdot; \cdot \vdash \sigma \Leftarrow (C_1; \cdot; \cdot)$.

$\langle 2 \rangle 1$. CASE: PAT_COMP_NO_SYM_ANNOT

PROOF: $term_1$ is a wildcard (fresh variable) which would unify with $pval$; let $\sigma = \cdot$ for SUBS_PAT_VALUE_NO_SYM_ANNOT / SUBS_CHK_EMPTY.

$\langle 2 \rangle 2$. CASE: PAT_COMP_SYM_ANNOT, PAT_SYM_OR_PAT_SYM

PROOF: $term_1 = x$, a fresh pattern variable, so would unify with $pval$;
let $\sigma = pval / x$ for SUBS_PAT_VALUE_SYM_ANNOT / SUBS_CHK_COMP (using $\cdot \vdash pval \Rightarrow \beta$).

$\langle 2 \rangle 3$. CASE: PAT_COMP_NIL

PROOF: $term_1 = \text{nil}$, and by inversion on the typing assumption, and then by exhaustiveness, $pval = \text{Nil } \beta()$, so would unify; let $\sigma = \cdot$ for SUBS_PAT_VALUE_NIL / SUBS_CHK_EMPTY.

$\langle 2 \rangle 4$. CASE: PAT_COMP_CONS

PROOF: $term_1 = term_{11} :: term_{12}$, and by inversion on the typing assumption, and then by exhaustiveness, $pval = \text{Cons}(pval_1, pval_2)$. By induction (1) they would unify and (2) let $\sigma = [\sigma_1, \sigma_2]$ for SUBS_PAT_VALUE_CONS / SUBS_CHK_COMP and SUBS_CHK_CONCAT (both are independent).

$\langle 2 \rangle 5$. CASE: PAT_COMP_TUPLE

PROOF: $term_1 = (\overline{term}_i^i)$, and by inversion on the typing assumption,
 $pval = \text{Tuple}(\overline{pval}_i^i)$. By induction (1) they would unify
(2) let $\sigma = [\overline{\sigma}_i^i]$ for SUBS_PAT_VALUE_TUPLE / SubsChkComp and SUBS_CHK_CONCAT.

$\langle 2 \rangle 6$. CASE: PAT_COMP_ARRAY

PROOF: Similar to PAT_COMP_TUPLE, but with SUBS_PAT_VALUE_ARRAY.

$\langle 2 \rangle 7$. CASE: PAT_COMP_SPECIFIED

PROOF: By induction we have (1) $term_1 \sim pval$, and by the Specified exception (see Section B4, Proof Judgements) $term_1 \sim \text{Specified}(pval)$;
 σ for SUBS_PAT_VALUE_SPECIFIED, typing by induction.

$\langle 2 \rangle 8$. CASE: PAT_SYM_OR_PAT_PAT

PROOF: By induction.

$\langle 1 \rangle 3$. CASE: PAT_RET_LOG

$C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \log y', \overline{ret_pat}_j^j : \exists y:\beta. ret \rightsquigarrow C_2; y':\beta, \mathcal{L}_2; \Phi_2; \mathcal{R}_2$

which means $fun = \forall x:\beta. fun'$ (by inversion, REL_RET_LOG)

and so $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash oarg, \overline{ret_term}_j^j :: \forall x:\beta. fun' \gg \mathbf{I}$ (by inversion, EXPL_SPINE_LOG).

$C; \mathcal{L}, y:\beta; \Phi \vdash \overline{ret_pat}_j^j : ret' \rightsquigarrow C_2; \mathcal{L}_2; \Phi_2; \mathcal{R}_2$ (from the pattern-matching assumption),

$\forall oarg \sim oarg'. \Phi \vdash oarg/x(fun') \sim oarg'/y'(ret')$ (from the related assumption),
 $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \overline{ret_term_j^j} :: oarg/x(fun') \gg \mathbf{I}$ (from the spine typing assumption)
 and $\Phi \vdash h \leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}$, imply $\langle h + f; \overline{ret_pat_j} = \overline{ret_term_j^j} \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h'' + f; \sigma \rangle$
 and $\exists \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ such that $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; y':\beta; \Phi \vdash h' \leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ and $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; y':\beta; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}'' \vdash \sigma_2 \leftarrow (\mathcal{C}_2; \mathcal{L}_2; \mathcal{R}_2)$ (by induction).

Since $\cdot; \cdot \vdash oarg \Rightarrow \beta$, and $oarg/y'(\Phi) = \Phi$ (because it is well-scoped / doesn't refer to y')
 and $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; oarg/y'(\Phi); oarg/y'(\underline{\mathcal{R}}') \vdash [\text{id}, oarg/y'] \leftarrow (\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; y':\beta; \underline{\mathcal{R}}')$,
 we have $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash oarg/y'(h'') \leftarrow oarg/y'(\underline{\mathcal{R}}'')$, and
 $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; oarg/y'(\underline{\mathcal{R}}'') \vdash oarg/y'(\sigma_2) \leftarrow (\mathcal{C}_2; \mathcal{L}_2; oarg/y'(\mathcal{R}_2))$ (by lemma B7.3 (Substitution)).

LET: $h' = oarg/y'(h'')$, $\sigma = [oarg/y', \sigma_2]$ to step with SUBS_PAT_RET_LOG.

$\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = oarg/y'(\underline{\mathcal{R}}'')$.

So $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash h' \leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$

and $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \sigma \leftarrow (\mathcal{C}_2; y':\beta; \mathcal{L}_2; \mathcal{R}_2)$ by SUBS_CHK_CONCAT.

(1)4. CASE: PAT_RET_PHI

$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \overline{ret_pat_i^i} : term' \wedge ret' \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi', term'; \mathcal{R}'$

which means $fun = term \supset fun'$ (by inversion, REL_RET_PHI),

and so $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \overline{ret_term_j^j} :: term * fun' \gg \mathbf{I}$ (by inversion, EXPL_SPINE_RES).

$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \overline{ret_pat_i^i} : ret' \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi', term'; \mathcal{R}'$ (from the pattern-matching assumption)

$\Phi \vdash fun' \sim ret'$ (from the related assumption),

$\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \overline{ret_term_j^j} :: fun' \gg \mathbf{I}$ (from the spine typing assumption)

imply $\langle h + f; \overline{ret_pat_i^i} = \overline{ret_term_i^i} \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h' + f; \sigma \rangle$ and the heap and substitution typings (by induction).

(1)5. CASE: PAT_RET_RES

$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{res } res_pat, ret_pat : res' * ret' \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_4; \mathcal{L}_3, \mathcal{L}_4; \Phi_3, \Phi_4; \mathcal{R}_3, \mathcal{R}_4$

which means $fun = res * fun'$ (by inversion, REL_RET_RES),

and so $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2 \vdash res_term, spine :: res * fun' \gg \mathbf{I}$ (by inversion, EXPL_SPINE_RES),

and $h = h_1 + h_2$ where $\Phi \vdash h_1 \leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1$ and $\Phi \vdash h_2 \leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2$ (by lemma B8.4).

$\cdot; \cdot; \cdot; \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1 \vdash res_term \leftarrow res$ (from the spine typing assumption)

and $\Phi \vdash h_1 \leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1$, imply $\exists res_val, \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1, h'_1$ such that $\Phi \vdash h'_1 \leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1$, $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1 \vdash res_val \leftarrow res'$

and $\langle h_1 + h_2 + f; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h'_1 + h_2 + f; res_val \rangle$ (by lemma B8.6 (Progress and type preservation for resource terms)).

$\mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash res_pat : res' \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}_3; \Phi_3; \mathcal{R}_3$ (from the pattern matching assumption),

$\Phi \vdash res \sim res'$ (from the related assumption),

$\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1 \vdash res_val \leftarrow res$ and $\Phi \vdash h'_1 \leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1$, imply

$\exists h''_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}''_1$ such that $\langle h'_1 + h_2 + f; res_pat = res_val \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h''_1 + h_2 + f; \sigma_1 \rangle$ $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash h''_1 \leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}''_1$,

and $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}''_1 \vdash \sigma_1 \leftarrow (\cdot; \mathcal{L}_3; \mathcal{R}_3)$ (by the nested proof below).

$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \overline{ret_pat_j^j} : ret' \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_4; \mathcal{L}_4; \Phi_4; \mathcal{R}_4$ (from the pattern matching assumption),

$\Phi \vdash fun' \sim ret'$ (from the related assumption),

$\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2 \vdash \overline{ret_term_j^j} :: fun' \gg \mathbf{I}$ (from the spine typing assumption),
and $\Phi \vdash h_2 \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2$, imply $\langle h_2 + h_1'' + f; \overline{ret_pat_j} = \overline{ret_term_j^j} \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h_2' + h_1'' + f; \sigma_2 \rangle$ and $\exists \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2'$
such that $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash h_2' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2'$, and $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2' \vdash \sigma_2 \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}_4; \mathcal{L}_4; \mathcal{R}_4)$ (by induction).

LET: $h' = h_1'' + h_2'$
 $\sigma = [\sigma_1, \sigma_2]$ to step with SUBS_PAT_RET_RES.
 $\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2'$.

So $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ by HEAP_CONCAT
and $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \sigma \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}_4; \mathcal{L}_3, \mathcal{L}_4; \mathcal{R}_3, \mathcal{R}_4)$ by SUBS_CHK_CONCAT
(because $\underline{\mathcal{R}}_2'$ is well-formed w.r.t. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}$, it does not contain any variables from $\mathcal{L}_3; \mathcal{R}_3$ so
 $\sigma_1(\underline{\mathcal{R}}_2') = \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2'$).

ASSUME: 1. $\mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash res_pat: res' \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$
2. $\Phi \vdash res \sim res'$
3. $\exists \underline{\mathcal{R}}. (\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash res_val \Leftarrow res) \wedge (\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}})$

PROVE: $\exists h', \sigma$.
 $\forall f. \langle h + f; res_pat = res_val \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h' + f; \sigma \rangle$
 $\exists \underline{\mathcal{R}}'. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \wedge \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \sigma \Leftarrow (\cdot; \mathcal{L}'; \mathcal{R}')$.

$\langle 2 \rangle 1$. CASE: PAT_RES_MATCH_FOLD

$\mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash fold(res_pat'): \alpha(ptr', \overline{iarg_i^i})(oarg') \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$
which means $res = \alpha(ptr', \overline{iarg_i^i})(oarg)$ (by inversion, REL_RES_PRED)
and so $\underline{\mathcal{R}} = \cdot: \alpha(ptr', \overline{iarg_i^i})(oarg)$ and $res_val = \alpha(ptr_2, \overline{iarg_2^i})$ (by lemma B8.3).

$\langle 3 \rangle 1$. $h = \{\alpha(ptr', \overline{iarg_i^i})(oarg) \& def \& heap\}$
PROOF: $\alpha \neq \mathbf{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle$ (from the pattern-matching assumption), and
lemma B8.4 (Normalised resource context determines structure of heap).

$\langle 3 \rangle 2$. $\exists \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1'$.

1. $\alpha \equiv x_p: \mathbf{pointer}, \overline{x_i: \beta_i^i}, y: \mathbf{record} \overline{tag_j: \beta_j^j} \mapsto res'' \in \mathbf{Globals}$
2. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1' \vdash def \Leftarrow [oarg/y, [\overline{iarg/x_i^i}], ptr/x_p](res'')$
3. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash heap \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1'$
PROOF: By inversion, $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}$ is HEAP_PRED_OTHER.

$\langle 3 \rangle 3$. $\mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash res_pat': [oarg'/y, [\overline{iarg'_i/x_i^i}], ptr'/x_p](res'') \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$
PROOF: By inversion on the pattern-matching assumption.

$\langle 3 \rangle 4$. $\Phi \vdash [oarg'/y, [\overline{iarg'_i/x_i^i}], ptr'/x_p](res'') \sim [oarg'/y, [\overline{iarg'_i/x_i^i}], ptr'/x_p](res'')$
PROOF: By lemma B9.2, using $\Phi \vdash res'' \sim res''$ (by lemma B9.1) and $ptr \sim ptr'$,
 $\overline{iarg_i} \sim \overline{iarg'_i}$ and $oarg \sim oarg'$.

$\langle 3 \rangle 5$. $\langle heap + f; res_pat = res_val \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h' + f; \sigma \rangle$
PROOF: By induction, using $\langle 3 \rangle 2$, $\langle 3 \rangle 3$ and $\langle 3 \rangle 4$.

$\langle 3 \rangle 6$. Step with SUBS_PAT_RES_FOLD.

$\langle 3 \rangle 7$. $h', \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ as given by induction.

⟨2⟩2. CASE: PAT_RES_MATCH_EMP / PAT_RES_MATCH_PHI
 $res = \mathbf{emp}$ or $term$ (by inversion, REL_RES_EMP / REL_RES_PHI) and so
 $res_val = \mathbf{emp}$ or \mathbf{term} and $\underline{\mathcal{R}} = \cdot$ (by lemma B8.3), meaning $h = \cdot$ (by lemma B8.4).
 PROOF: Let $h' = \cdot$ to step with SUBS_PAT_RES_EMP / SUBS_PAT_RES_PHI.
 $\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = \cdot$, so HEAP_EMPTY and SUBS_CHK_EMPTY suffice.

⟨2⟩3. CASE: PAT_RES_MATCH_IF_TRUE / PAT_RES_MATCH_IF_FALSE
 Only showing true case, false case is symmetric.

$res' = \mathbf{if} \ term' \ \mathbf{then} \ res'_1 \ \mathbf{else} \ res'_2$ so
 $res = \mathbf{if} \ term \ \mathbf{then} \ res_1 \ \mathbf{else} \ res_2$ (by inversion, REL_RES_IF).

Since $\mathbf{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow term')$ (from the pattern-matching assumption) and
 $\mathbf{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow term \leftrightarrow term')$, we can conclude the typing assumption must be RES_CHK_IF_TRUE.

From there, we proceed by induction.

⟨2⟩4. CASE: PAT_RES_MATCH_VAR
 PROOF: Let $h' = h$ to step with SUBS_PAT_RES_VAR.
 $\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = \underline{\mathcal{R}}$ so SUBS_CHK_RES.

⟨2⟩5. CASE: PAT_RES_MATCH_SEPCONJ
 $\mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \langle res_pat_1, res_pat_2 \rangle : res'_1 * res'_2 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}_1, \mathcal{L}_2; \Phi_1, \Phi_2; \mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2$

$res = res_1 * res_2$ (by inversion, REL_RES_SEPCONJ) and
 $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2 \vdash \langle res_val_1, res_val_2 \rangle \Leftarrow res_1 * res_2$ (by lemma B8.3),
 so $h = h_1 + h_2$ where $\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1$ and $\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2$.

By induction, obtain h'_1 and h'_2 , and then let $h' = h'_1 + h'_2$. Instantiate the frame, from
 the inductive hypothesis with $h_2 + f$ and then $h'_1 + f$ to conclude
 $\langle h_1 + h_2 + f; res_pat_1 = res_val_1 \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h'_1 + h_2 + f; \sigma_1 \rangle$ and
 $\langle h_2 + h'_1 + f; res_pat_2 = res_val_2 \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h'_2 + h'_1 + f; \sigma_2 \rangle$ to step with SUBS_PAT_RES_PAIR.
 LET: $\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_2$ (obtained from induction).
 We then have and $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash h'_1 + h'_2 \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ and (since $\sigma_1(\mathcal{R}_2) = \mathcal{R}_2$ because it can not
 refer to \mathcal{L}_1) $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash [\sigma_1, \sigma_2] \Leftarrow (\cdot; \mathcal{L}_1, \mathcal{L}_2; \mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2)$.

⟨2⟩6. CASE: PAT_RES_MATCH_PACK
 $\mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \mathbf{pack}(x, res_pat') : \exists y' : \beta. res'_1 \rightsquigarrow x : \beta, \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$

$res = \exists y : \beta. res_1$ (by inversion, REL_RES_EXISTS) and
 $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \mathbf{pack}(oarg, res_val') \Leftarrow \exists y : \beta. res_1$ (by lemma B8.3).
 $\mathcal{L}, x : \beta; \Phi \vdash res_pat' : x / y'(res'_1) \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$ (from the pattern-matching assumption),
 $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash res_val' \Leftarrow oarg / y(res_1)$ (from the typing assumption),
 $\forall term \sim term'. \Phi \vdash term / y(res_1) \sim term' / y'(res'_1)$ (from the related assumption),
 $oarg \sim x$ imply $\exists h'', \sigma', \dots \forall f \dots$
 and $\exists \underline{\mathcal{R}}''. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}, x : \beta; \Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \wedge \mathcal{C}; x : \beta, \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}'' \vdash \sigma' \Leftarrow (\cdot; \mathcal{L}'; \mathcal{R}')$

Since $\cdot; \cdot \vdash oarg \Rightarrow \beta$, and $oarg / x(\Phi) = \Phi$ (because it is well-scoped / doesn't refer to

x) and $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; oarg/x(\Phi); oarg/x(\underline{\mathcal{R}}') \vdash [\text{id}, oarg/x] \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}; x:\beta, \mathcal{L}'; \underline{\mathcal{R}}')$,
we have $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash oarg/x(h'') \Leftarrow oarg/x(\underline{\mathcal{R}}'')$, and
 $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; oarg/x(\underline{\mathcal{R}}'') \vdash oarg/x(\sigma') \Leftarrow (\cdot; \mathcal{L}'; oarg/x(\mathcal{R}_2))$ (by lemma B7.3
(Substitution)).

LET: $h' = oarg/x(h'')$
 $\sigma = [oarg/x, \sigma']$ to step with SUBS_PAT_RES_PACK.
 $\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = oarg/x(\underline{\mathcal{R}}'')$ so $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; oarg/x(\underline{\mathcal{R}}'') \vdash [oarg/x, \sigma'] \Leftarrow (\cdot; \mathcal{L}'; \mathcal{R}_2)$ by SUBS-
CHK_CONCAT.

B9.5 $\Phi \vdash \text{to_fun } ret \sim ret$

PROOF SKETCH: Induction over ret .

B9.6 Statement and proof

ASSUME: 1. Closed (no free-variables) expression $texpr$.
2. $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash texpr \Leftarrow ret$
3. All patterns in $texpr$ are exhaustive.

PROVE: Either $texpr$ is a value $tval$, or it is unreachable, or
 $\forall h, \underline{\mathcal{R}}. (\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}) \Rightarrow \exists h', texpr'. \langle h; texpr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; texpr' \rangle$.

PROOF SKETCH: Induction over the typing rules.

<1>1. CASE: Value typing rules (see B5.3).

PROOF: All these judgements/rules give types to syntactic values; and there are no operational rules corresponding to them (see Section B3).

<1>2. CASE: PURE_TOP_VAL_UNDEF, PURE_TOP_VAL_ERROR, EXPL_TOP_VAL_UNDEF, EXPL-
TOP_VAL_ERROR.

PROOF: All these rules require inconsistent constraint context, and so would be unreachable.

<1>3. CASE: PURE_EXPR_ARRAY_SHIFT.

PROOF: By inversion on $\cdot \vdash pval_1 \Rightarrow \text{pointer}$, $pval_1$ must be a mem_ptr (PURE_VAL_OBJ-
PTR). Similarly $pval_2$ must be a mem_int , so step with PE_TP_ARRAY_SHIFT.

<1>4. CASE: PURE_EXPR_MEMBER_SHIFT.

PROOF: $pval$ must be a mem_ptr so step with PE_TP_MEMBER_SHIFT.

<1>5. CASE: PURE_EXPR_NOT.

PROOF: $pval$ must be a $bool_value$ so step with PE_TP_NOT_TRUE or PE_TP_NOT_FALSE.

<1>6. CASE: PURE_EXPR_ARITH_BINOP, PURE_EXPR_REL_BINOP.

PROOF: $pval_1$ and $pval_2$ must be mem_ints , so step with PE_TP_ARITH_BINOP or PE_TP-
REL_BINOP respectively.

⟨1⟩7. CASE: PURE_EXPR_BOOL_BINOP.

PROOF: $pval_1$ and $pval_2$ must be *bool_values*, so step with PE_TP_BOOL_BINOP.

⟨1⟩8. CASE: PURE_EXPR_CALL.

⟨2⟩1. 1. $name: pure_fun \equiv \overline{x_i}^i \mapsto texpr \in \text{Globals}$.

2. $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \overline{pval_i}^i :: pure_fun \gg \Sigma y:\beta. term \wedge \mathbb{I}$.

PROOF: By inversion on the assumption.

⟨2⟩2. $\langle \cdot; \overline{x_i = pval_i}^i \rangle :: pure_fun \gg \langle \cdot; \sigma; \Sigma y:\beta. term \wedge \mathbb{I} \rangle$.

PROOF: By lemma B9.3.

⟨2⟩3. Thus it can step with PE_TP_CALL.

⟨1⟩9. CASE: PURE_EXPR_ASSERT_UNDEF.

⟨2⟩1. $pval$ must be a *bool_value* PROOF: By PURE_VAL_TRUE, PURE_VAL_FALSE.

⟨2⟩2. $smt(\Phi \Rightarrow pval)$. PROOF: By inversion on the assumption.

⟨2⟩3. If it is **False**, then by the latter, we have an inconsistent constraints context, meaning the code is unreachable.

⟨2⟩4. If it is **True**, we may step with PE_TP_ASSERT_UNDEF.

⟨1⟩10. CASE: PURE_EXPR_BOOL_TO_INTEGER.

PROOF: $pval$ must be a *bool_value* (PURE_VAL_TRUE, PURE_VAL_FALSE) and so step with PE_TP_BOOL_TO_INTEGER_TRUE, PE_TP_BOOL_TO_INTEGER_FALSE respectively.

⟨1⟩11. CASE: PURE_EXPR_WRAP_I.

PROOF: $pval$ must be a *mem_int* (PURE_VAL_OBJ_PTR) and so step with PE_TP_WRAP_I.

⟨1⟩12. CASE: PURE_TOP_IF, PURE_TOP_CASE, PURE_TOP_LET, PURE_TOP_LETT.

PROOF: See EXPL_TOP_SEQ_IF, EXPL_TOP_SEQ_CASE, EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LET, EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LETT, case for more general proofs.

⟨1⟩13. CASE: EXPL_IS_ACTION_CREATE.

⟨2⟩1. $pval$ must be a *mem_int*.

PROOF: By PURE_VAL_OBJ_PTR.

⟨2⟩2. h must be \cdot (empty).

PROOF: By HEAP_EMPTY.

⟨2⟩3. Step with ACTION_IS_CREATE.

PROOF: mem_ptr is free in the premises and so can be constructed to satisfy the requirements.

⟨1⟩14. CASE: EXPL_IS_ACTION_LOAD.

- ⟨2⟩1. $pval_0$ must be a *mem_ptr*.
 PROOF: By PURE_VAL_OBJ_PTR.
- ⟨2⟩2. $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash res_term \Rightarrow term \xrightarrow{\tau}^{init} pval_1$.
 $\text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow (term = mem_ptr) \wedge (init = \text{const}_\tau \text{true}))$.
 PROOF: By inversion on the typing assumption and ⟨2⟩1.
- ⟨2⟩3. $\exists h', \underline{\mathcal{R}}', res_val$.
 1. $\Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$
 2. $\langle h; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h'; res_val \rangle$
 3. $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash res_val \Rightarrow term \xrightarrow{\tau}^{init} pval_1$
 PROOF: By ⟨2⟩2 and lemma B8.6 (Progress and type preservation for resource terms).
- ⟨2⟩4. $res_val = \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (term)$.
 PROOF: By lemma B8.3 (Non-conditional resources determine context and values).
- ⟨2⟩5. $h' = \{ term \xrightarrow{\tau}^{init} pval_1 \ \& \ \text{None} \}$.
 PROOF: By inversion on the term typing assumption in ⟨2⟩3 using ⟨2⟩4, $\Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ and lemma B8.4 (Normalised resource context determines structure of heap).
- ⟨2⟩6. Step with ACTION_IS_LOAD.
- ⟨1⟩15. CASE: EXPL_IS_ACTION_STORE.
- ⟨2⟩1. $pval_0$ must both be a *mem_ptr*.
 PROOF: By PURE_VAL_OBJ_PTR.
- ⟨2⟩2. $\text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{representable}(\tau, pval_1))$
 $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash res_term \Rightarrow term \xrightarrow{\tau}$
 $\text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow term = mem_ptr)$.
 PROOF: By inversion on the typing assumption and ⟨2⟩1.
- ⟨2⟩3. $\exists h', \underline{\mathcal{R}}', res_val$.
 1. $\Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$
 2. $\langle h; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h'; res_val \rangle$
 3. $\cdot; \cdot; \cdot; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash res_val \Rightarrow term \xrightarrow{\tau}$.
 PROOF: By ⟨2⟩2 and lemma B8.6 (Progress and type preservation for resource terms).
- ⟨2⟩4. $res_val = \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (term)$.
 PROOF: By lemma B8.3 (Non-conditional resources determine context and values).
- ⟨2⟩5. $h' = \{ term \xrightarrow{\tau} \ \& \ \text{None} \}$.
 PROOF: By inversion on the term typing assumption in ⟨2⟩3, $\Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ and lemma B8.4 (Normalised resource context determines structure of heap).
- ⟨2⟩6. Step with ACTION_IS_STORE.
- ⟨1⟩16. CASE: EXPL_IS_ACTION_KILL_STATIC

- ⟨2⟩1. $pval$ must be a mem_ptr .
PROOF: By PURE_VAL_OBJ_PTR.
- ⟨2⟩2. $.; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash res_term \Rightarrow term \mapsto_{\tau} _$
 $smt(\Phi \Rightarrow term = mem_ptr)$.
PROOF: By inversion on the typing assumption and ⟨2⟩1.
- ⟨2⟩3. $\exists h', \underline{\mathcal{R}'}, res_val$.
1. $\Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$
2. $\langle h; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h'; res_val \rangle$
3. $.; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}'} \vdash res_val \Rightarrow term \mapsto_{\tau} _$.
PROOF: By ⟨2⟩2 and lemma B8.6 (Progress and type preservation for resource terms).
- ⟨2⟩4. $res_val = \mathbf{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (term)$.
PROOF: By lemma B8.3 (Non-conditional resources determine context and values).
- ⟨2⟩5. $h' = \{term \mapsto_{\tau} _ \ \& \ \mathbf{None}\}$.
PROOF: By inversion on the typing assumption in ⟨2⟩3, $\Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$ and lemma B8.4 (Normalised resource context determines structure of heap).
- ⟨2⟩6. Step with ACTION_IS_KILL_STATIC.
- ⟨1⟩17. CASE: EXPL_IS_MEMOP_REL_BINOP.
PROOF: Similar to PURE_EXPR_REL_BINOP, but step with MEMOP_IS_REL_BINOP.
- ⟨1⟩18. CASE: EXPL_IS_MEMOP_INTFROMPTR.
PROOF: $pval$ must be a mem_ptr , so step with MEMOP_IS_INTFROMPTR.
- ⟨1⟩19. CASE: EXPL_IS_MEMOP_PTRFROMINT.
PROOF: $pval$ must be a mem_int , so step with MEMOP_IS_PTRFROMINT.
- ⟨1⟩20. CASE: EXPL_IS_MEMOP_PTRVALIDFORDEREF.
- ⟨2⟩1. $pval$ must be a mem_ptr .
PROOF: By PURE_VAL_OBJ_PTR.
- ⟨2⟩2. $.; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash res_term \Rightarrow term \xrightarrow{\tau}^{init} _$.
 $smt(\Phi \Rightarrow (term = mem_ptr) \wedge (init = \mathbf{const}_{\tau} \mathbf{true}))$.
PROOF: By inversion on the typing assumption and ⟨2⟩1.
- ⟨2⟩3. $\exists h' \underline{\mathcal{R}'}, res_val$.
1. $\Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$
2. $\langle h; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h'; res_val \rangle$
3. $.; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}'} \vdash res_val \Rightarrow term \xrightarrow{\tau}^{init} _$.
PROOF: By ⟨2⟩2 and lemma B8.6 (Progress and type preservation for resource terms).
- ⟨2⟩4. $res_val = \mathbf{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (term)$.

PROOF: By lemma B8.3 (Non-conditional resources determine context and values).

⟨2⟩5. $h' = \{term \xrightarrow{\tau} \text{init} _ \& \text{None}\}$.

PROOF: By inversion on the typing assumption in ⟨2⟩3 using ⟨2⟩4, $\Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$ and lemma B8.4 (Normalised resource context determines structure of heap).

⟨2⟩6. Step with MEMOP_IS_PTRVALIDFORDEREF.

⟨1⟩21. CASE: EXPL_IS_MEMOP_PTRWELLALIGNED.

PROOF: $pval$ must be a mem_ptr , so step with MEMOP_IS_PTRWELLALIGNED.

⟨1⟩22. CASE: EXPL_IS_MEMOP_PTRARRAYSHIFT.

PROOF: $pval_1$ must be a mem_ptr and $pval_2$ must be a mem_int , so step with MEMOP_IS_PTRARRAYSHIFT.

⟨1⟩23. CASE: EXPL_SEQ_CCALL.

⟨2⟩1. $ident:fun \equiv \overline{x_i}^i \mapsto \text{texpr} \in \text{Globals}$
 $;; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \overline{spine_elem_i}^i :: fun \gg ret$.

PROOF: By inversion.

⟨2⟩2. $\langle h; \overline{x_i = spine_elem_i}^i \rangle :: fun \gg \langle h'; \sigma_2; ret \rangle$.

PROOF: By ⟨2⟩1 and lemma B9.3 (Well-typed spines produce substitutions and the same return type).

⟨2⟩3. Step with SEQ_T_CCALL.

⟨1⟩24. CASE: EXPL_SEQ_PROC, EXPL_TOP_SEQ_RUN.

PROOF: Similar to EXPL_SEQ_CCALL, but step with SEQ_T_PROC / TSEQ_T_RUN.

⟨1⟩25. CASE: EXPL_IS_MEMOP.

PROOF: By induction, if $memop$ is unreachable, then the whole expression is so. $memops$ are not values. Only stepping cases applies, so step with IS_IS_MEMOP.

⟨1⟩26. CASE: EXPL_IS_ACTION, EXPL_IS_NEG_ACTION.

PROOF: By induction, if $action$ is unreachable, then the whole expression is so. $actions$ are not values. Only stepping case applies, so step with IS_IS_ACTION (or IS_IS_NEG_ACTION respectively).

⟨1⟩27. CASE: EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LETP, EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LETP.

PROOF: See EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LET / EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LETT for more general cases and proofs.

⟨1⟩28. CASE: EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LET.

PROOF: By induction, since seq_expr is not value, if it is unreachable, the whole expression is so. If seq_expr takes a step, the whole expression steps with TSEQ_T_LET_LETT.

⟨1⟩29. CASE: EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LETT.

PROOF: By induction, if $texpr$ is unreachable, so is the whole expression.

If it is a $tval$, use lemma B9.4 (Well-typed values pattern-match successfully), with lemma B9.5 ($\Phi \vdash \text{to_fun } ret \sim ret$) and the assumption that all patterns are exhaustive, so the whole expression steps with TSEQ_T_LETT_SUB.

If $texpr$ takes a step, the whole expression steps with TSEQ_T_LETT_LETT.

(1)30. CASE: EXPL_TOP_SEQ_CASE.

PROOF: By assumption that all patterns are exhaustive, and lemma B9.4 (Well-typed values pattern-match successfully), there is at least one pattern against which $pval$ will match, so TSEQ_T_CASE.

(1)31. CASE: EXPL_TOP_SEQ_IF.

PROOF: $pval$ must be a $bool_value$ and so TSEQ_T_IF_TRUE/ TSEQ_T_IF_FALSE.

(1)32. CASE: EXPL_TOP_SEQ_BOUND.

PROOF: Step with TSEQ_T_BOUND.

(1)33. CASE: EXPL_TOP_IS_LETS.

PROOF: Similar to EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LETT, but step with TIS_T_LETS_SUB / TIS_T_LETS_LETSinstead.

(1)34. CASE: EXPL_TOP_SEQ, EXPL_TOP_IS.

PROOF: Step with T_T_TSEQ_T / T_T_TIS_T respectively.

B10 Type Preservation

B10.1 Owned $\langle \tau \rangle$ resource output values have type β_τ

If $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (ptr) \Leftarrow ptr' \xrightarrow{\text{init}} pval$ then $\mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \beta_\tau$ and $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash \text{init} \Rightarrow \text{bool}_\tau$.

PROOF SKETCH: Induction over the typing judgements. Only `EXPL_IS_ACTION_STORE` constrain `..value` of `Owned` $\langle \tau \rangle$ resources, and its premises ensure it has type β_τ ; `EXPL_IS_ACTION_LOAD` and `EXPL_IS_MEMOP_PTRVALIDFORDEREF` simply propagate the value. `EXPL_IS_ACTION_CREATE`, `EXPL_IS_ACTION_LOAD` and `EXPL_IS_ACTION_STORE` and ensure `..init` has type bool_τ .

B10.2 Type Preservation Statement and Proof

If $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{texpr} \Leftarrow \text{ret}$ and $\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \mathcal{R}$, and all top-level functions are well-typed¹ then $\forall f. \langle h + f; \text{texpr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{heap}; \text{texpr}' \rangle \Rightarrow \exists \Phi', h', \mathcal{R}'. (\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \cdot \sqsubseteq \cdot; \cdot; \Phi'; \cdot) \wedge \text{heap} = h' + f \wedge (\Phi' \vdash h' \Leftarrow \mathcal{R}') \wedge (\cdot; \cdot; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}' \vdash \text{texpr}' \Leftarrow \text{ret})$.

You can equally well prove $\forall \mathcal{R}'. \Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \mathcal{R}' \Rightarrow \cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \mathcal{R}' \vdash \text{texpr}' \Leftarrow \text{ret}$ instead. Instead of supplying \mathcal{R}' and proving heap typing, you instead invert heap typing to deduce that \mathcal{R}' can only be what you would have supplied anyways.

It's worth noting that the constraint context will always only contain trivially true constraints (since $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}$ are both empty, all the *terms* in $\Phi; \mathcal{R}$ will be closed). This does not, by itself, guarantee that all conditional resources will be determined (e.g. `if default bool then res1 else res2`), but there are other ways of excluding this (not allowing under-determined in heaps).

PROOF SKETCH: Induction over the typing rules, which don't refer to values or unreachable program points.

ASSUME: 1. $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{texpr} \Leftarrow \text{ret}$,
 2. $\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \mathcal{R}$
 3. all top-level functions are well-typed
 4. $\forall f. \langle h + f; \text{texpr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{heap}; \text{texpr}' \rangle$

PROVE: $\exists \Phi', h', \mathcal{R}'$.
 1. $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \cdot \sqsubseteq \cdot; \cdot; \Phi'; \cdot$
 2. $\text{heap} = h' + f$
 3. $\Phi' \vdash h' \Leftarrow \mathcal{R}'$
 4. $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}' \vdash \text{texpr}' \Leftarrow \text{ret}$.

(1)1. CASE: `PURE_EXPR_ARRAY_SHIFT`.

For all pure expressions, $\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \cdot$, $h = \cdot$, $\text{heap} = f$.

LET: $h' = \cdot$ and $\mathcal{R}' = \cdot$, so $\text{heap} = h' + f$ trivially and $\Phi \vdash \cdot \Leftarrow \cdot$ (by `HEAP_EMPTY`).

$\text{ret} = \Sigma y:\text{pointer}. y = \text{mem_ptr} +_{\text{ptr}} (\text{mem_int} \times \text{size_of}(\tau)) \wedge \text{I}$

PROOF: By `PURE_TOP_VAL_DONE`, suffices to show $\cdot \vdash \text{mem_ptr}' \Rightarrow \text{pointer}$ (true by

¹More precisely, if $\text{ident}:\text{fun} \equiv \overline{x_i}^i \mapsto \text{texpr} \in \text{Globals}$ and $\overline{x_i}^i :: \text{fun} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}''; \mathcal{L}''; \Phi''; \mathcal{R}'' \mid \text{ret}''$ then $\mathcal{C}''; \mathcal{L}''; \Phi''; \mathcal{R}'' \vdash \text{texpr} \Leftarrow \text{ret}''$.

PURE_VAL_OBJ_PTR) and $\text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{mem_ptr}' = \text{mem_ptr} +_{\text{ptr}} (\text{mem_int} \times \text{size_of}(\tau)))$
 (true by definition of PE_TP_ARRAY_SHIFT).

(1)2. CASE: PURE_EXPR_MEMBER_SHIFT, PURE_EXPR_NOT, PURE_EXPR_ARITH_BINOP,
 PURE_EXPR_BOOL_BINOP, PURE_EXPR_REL_BINOP, PURE_EXPR_ASSERT_UNDEF,
 PURE_EXPR_BOOL_TO_INTEGER, PURE_EXPR_WRAPI.

PROOF: Similar to PURE_EXPR_ARRAY_SHIFT.

(1)3. CASE: PURE_EXPR_CALL

PROOF: See EXPL_SEQ_CCALL for a more general case and proof.

(1)4. CASE: PURE_TOP_IF.

PROOF: See EXPL_TOP_SEQ_IF for a more general case and proof.

(1)5. CASE: PURE_TOP_LET.

PROOF: See EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LET for a more general case and proof.

(1)6. CASE: PURE_TOP_LETT.

PROOF: See EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LETT for a more general case and proof.

(1)7. CASE: PURE_TOP_CASE.

PROOF: See EXPL_TOP_SEQ_CASE for a more general case and proof.

(1)8. CASE: EXPL_IS_ACTION_CREATE.

LET: $\text{ret} = \Sigma y_p:\text{pointer}. \text{term} \wedge (y_p \xrightarrow{\text{const}_\tau \text{false}} \text{default } \beta_\tau) * \text{I}$
 where $\text{term} = \text{representable}(\tau^*, y_p) \wedge \text{alignedI}(\text{mem_int}, y_p)$.
 $pt = \text{Owned}(\tau)(\text{mem_ptr})(\text{oarg})$ where
 $\text{oarg} = \{\text{init} = \text{const}_\tau \text{false}, \text{value} = \text{default } \beta_\tau\}$.

ASSUME: $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \text{create}(\text{mem_int}, \tau) \Rightarrow \text{ret}$ and so $h = \cdot$ (by inversion, HEAP_EMPTY)
 and $\text{heap} = f + \{pt \ \& \ \text{None}\}$.

LET: $h' = \{pt \ \& \ \text{None}\}$, $\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = \cdot; pt$.

This means $\text{heap} = h' + f$ (trivially) and $\Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ (by HEAP_PRED_OWNED).

PROVE: $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \text{done}(\text{mem_ptr}, \text{Owned}(\tau)(\text{mem_ptr})): \text{ret} \Rightarrow \text{ret}$.

(2)1. $\cdot \vdash \text{mem_ptr} \Rightarrow \text{pointer}$ by PURE_VAL_OBJ_PTR and PURE_VAL_OBJ.

(2)2. $\text{smt}(\cdot \Rightarrow \text{term})$ by construction of mem_ptr .

(2)3. $\cdot; \cdot; \cdot; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \text{Owned}(\tau)(\text{mem_ptr}) \Leftarrow pt$ by RES_SYN_PRED.

(2)4. Prove typing with EXPL_SPINE_RET; (2)3 – (2)1 with EXPL_SPINE_RES, EXPL_SPINE_PHI, EXPL_SPINE_COMP respectively; EXPL_IS_TVAL.

(1)9. CASE: EXPL_IS_ACTION_LOAD.

LET: $\text{ret} = \Sigma y:\beta_\tau. y = \text{pval} \wedge (\text{mem_ptr} \xrightarrow{\text{const}_\tau \text{true}} \text{pval}) * \text{I}$

$pt = \text{Owned } \langle \tau \rangle (\text{mem_ptr})(\text{oarg})$ where $\text{oarg} = \{\text{init} = \text{const}_\tau \text{true}, \text{value} = \text{pval}\}$.

ASSUME: $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{load } (\tau, \text{mem_ptr}, _, \text{res_term}) \Rightarrow \text{ret}$
 and $\text{heap} = \text{heap}' + \{pt \ \& \ \text{None}\}$ so
 $\langle h + f; \text{res_term} \rangle \Downarrow \langle \text{heap}' + \{pt \ \& \ \text{None}\}; \text{Owned } \langle \tau \rangle (\text{mem_ptr}) \rangle$.

LET: h' and $\underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ be as per lemma B8.8 (Resource term reduction is isolated).
 $\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = _:\text{pt}$ by lemma B8.3 and $h' = \{pt \ \& \ \text{None}\}$ by lemma B8.4, hence $\text{heap}' = f$.
 This means $\text{heap} = h' + f$, $\Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ and $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \text{Owned } \langle \tau \rangle (\text{mem_ptr}) \Rightarrow \text{pt}$.

PROVE: $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{done } \langle \text{pval}, \text{Owned } \langle \tau \rangle (\text{mem_ptr}) \rangle : \text{ret} \Rightarrow \text{ret}$.

$\langle 2 \rangle 1$. $\cdot \vdash \text{pval} \Rightarrow \beta_\tau$ by lemma B10.1 (Owned $\langle \tau \rangle$ resource output values have type β_τ).

$\langle 2 \rangle 2$. $\text{smt } (\cdot \Rightarrow \text{pval} = \text{pval})$ trivially.

$\langle 2 \rangle 3$. $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{Owned } \langle \tau \rangle (\text{mem_ptr}) \Rightarrow \text{pt}$, already established.

$\langle 2 \rangle 4$. Prove typing with EXPL_SPINE_RET; $\langle 2 \rangle 3 - \langle 2 \rangle 1$ with EXPL_SPINE_RES, EXPL_SPINE_LOG, EXPL_SPINE_COMP respectively; EXPL_IS_TVAL.

$\langle 1 \rangle 10$. CASE: EXPL_IS_ACTION_STORE.

LET: $\text{ret} = \Sigma _:\text{unit}. (\text{mem_ptr} \xrightarrow{\text{const}_\tau \text{true}} \text{pval}) * \text{I}$.
 $pt = \text{Owned } \langle \tau \rangle (\text{mem_ptr})(_)$, $pt' = \text{Owned } \langle \tau \rangle (\text{mem_ptr})(\text{oarg})$, where
 $\text{oarg} = \{\text{init} = \text{const}_\tau \text{true}, \text{value} = \text{pval}\}$.

ASSUME: $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{store } (_, \tau, \text{mem_ptr}, \text{pval}, _, \text{res_term}) \Rightarrow \text{ret}$ and
 $\text{heap} = \text{heap}' + \{pt' \ \& \ \text{None}\}$ so
 $\langle h + f; \text{res_term} \rangle \Downarrow \langle \text{heap}' + \{pt' \ \& \ \text{None}\}; \text{Owned } \langle \tau \rangle (\text{mem_ptr}) \rangle$.

$\exists h'', \underline{\mathcal{R}}''$ such that $\text{heap}' + \{pt' \ \& \ \text{None}\} = h'' + f$, $\Phi \vdash h'' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}''$ and
 $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}'' \vdash \text{Owned } \langle \tau \rangle (\text{mem_ptr}) \Rightarrow \text{pt}'$, by lemma B8.8 (Resource term reduction is isolated).

$\underline{\mathcal{R}}'' = _:\text{pt}'$ by lemma B8.3 and $h'' = \{pt' \ \& \ \text{None}\}$ by lemma B8.4, hence $\text{heap}' = f$.

LET: $h' = \{pt' \ \& \ \text{None}\}$ and $\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = _:\text{pt}'$.

This means $\text{heap} = h' + f$ and $\Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ (by HEAP_PRED_OWNED).

PROVE: $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{done } \langle \text{Unit}, \text{Owned } \langle \tau \rangle (\text{mem_ptr}) \rangle : \text{ret} \Rightarrow \text{ret}$.

$\langle 2 \rangle 1$. $\cdot \vdash \text{Unit} \Rightarrow \text{unit}$ by PURE_VAL_UNIT.

$\langle 2 \rangle 2$. $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; _:\text{pt}' \vdash \text{Owned } \langle \tau \rangle (\text{mem_ptr}) \Leftarrow \text{pt}'$ by RES_SYN_PRED.

$\langle 2 \rangle 3$. Prove typing with EXPL_SPINE_RET; $\langle 2 \rangle 2 - \langle 2 \rangle 1$ with EXPL_SPINE_RES, EXPL_SPINE_COMP respectively; EXPL_IS_TVAL.

$\langle 1 \rangle 11$. CASE: EXPL_IS_ACTION_KILL_STATIC.

ASSUME: $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{kill } (\text{static } \tau, \text{mem_ptr}, \text{res_term}) \Rightarrow \Sigma _:\text{unit}. \text{I}$ and

$\langle h + f; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle heap + \{pt \ \& \ \text{None}\}; \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (mem_ptr) \rangle$.

$\exists h'', \underline{\mathcal{R}}''$ such that $heap + \{pt \ \& \ \text{None}\} = h'' + f$, $\Phi \vdash h'' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}''$ and
 $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}'' \vdash \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (mem_ptr) \Rightarrow pt$, by lemma B8.8 (Resource term reduction is isolated).

$\underline{\mathcal{R}}'' = \cdot; pt$ by lemma B8.3 and $h'' = \{pt \ \& \ \text{None}\}$ by lemma B8.4, hence $heap = f$.

LET: $h' = \cdot$ and $\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = \cdot$.

This means $heap = h' + f$ and $\Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ (by HEAP_EMPTY).

PROVE: $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \text{done} \langle \text{Unit} \rangle; \Sigma \cdot; \text{unit}. \text{I} \Rightarrow \Sigma \cdot; \text{unit}. \text{I}$

PROOF: By EXPL_SPINE_RET, PURE_VAL_UNIT, EXPL_SPINE_COMP, EXPL_IS_TVAL.

(1)12. CASE: EXPL_IS_MEMOP_REL_BINOP.

PROOF: Similar to PURE_EXPR_REL_BINOP.

(1)13. CASE: EXPL_IS_MEMOP_INTFROMPTR.

LET: $ret = \Sigma y; \text{integer}. y = \text{cast_ptr_to_int } mem_ptr \wedge \text{I}$. Since $\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \cdot$, $h = \cdot$,
 $heap = f$.

ASSUME: $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \text{intFromPtr} (\tau_1, \tau_2, mem_ptr) \Rightarrow ret$.

LET: $h' = \cdot$ and $\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = \cdot$, so $heap = h' + f$ trivially and $\Phi \vdash \cdot \Leftarrow \cdot$ (by HEAP_EMPTY).

PROVE: $\cdot; \cdot; \cdot; \cdot \vdash \text{done} \langle mem_int \rangle; ret \Rightarrow ret$

PROOF: Prove typing with EXPL_SPINE_RET, EXPL_SPINE_PHI, EXPL_SPINE_COMP and EXPL_TOP_VAL_DONE instead.

(1)14. CASE: EXPL_IS_MEMOP_PTRFROMINT.

PROOF: Similar to EXPL_IS_MEMOP_INTFROMPTR, swapping base types `integer` and `pointer`.

(1)15. CASE: EXPL_IS_MEMOP_PTRVALIDFORDEREF.

LET: $pt = \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (mem_ptr) (oarg)$ where $oarg = \{init = \text{const}_\tau \text{true}, value = value\}$
 $ret = \Sigma y; \text{bool}. y = \text{aligned} (\tau, pval) \wedge pt * \text{I}$

ASSUME: $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{ptrValidForDeref} (\tau, mem_ptr, res_term) \Rightarrow ret$

and $heap = heap' + \{pt \ \& \ \text{None}\}$ so

$\langle h + f; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle heap' + \{pt \ \& \ \text{None}\}; \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (mem_ptr) \rangle$.

LET: h' and $\underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ be as per lemma B8.8 (Resource term reduction is isolated).

$\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = \cdot; pt$ by lemma B8.3 and $h' = \{pt \ \& \ \text{None}\}$ by lemma B8.4, hence $heap' = f$.

This means $heap = h' + f$, $\Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ and $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (mem_ptr) \Rightarrow pt$.

PROVE: $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \text{done} \langle bool_value, \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (mem_ptr) \rangle; ret \Rightarrow ret$.

(2)1. $\cdot \vdash bool_value \Rightarrow \text{bool}$ by PURE_VAL_TRUE/ PURE_VAL_FALSE.

(2)2. $\text{smt} (\cdot \Rightarrow bool_value = \text{aligned} (\tau, mem_ptr))$.

PROOF: By construction of `bool_value` (inversion on the transition).

- ⟨2⟩3. $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \cdot; pt \vdash \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (mem_ptr) \Leftarrow pt$, already established.
- ⟨2⟩4. Prove typing with `EXPL_SPINE_RET`; ⟨2⟩3 – ⟨2⟩1 with `EXPL_SPINE_RES`, `EXPL_SPINE_PHI`, `EXPL_SPINE_COMP` respectively; `EXPL_Is_TVAL`.
- ⟨1⟩16. CASE: `EXPL_Is_MEMOP_PTRWELLALIGNED`.
 LET: $ret = \Sigma y:\text{bool}. y = \text{aligned}(\tau, mem_ptr) \wedge \text{I}$.
 ASSUME: $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \text{ptrWellAligned}(\tau, mem_ptr) \Rightarrow ret$.
 Since $\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \cdot, h = \cdot, heap = f$.
 LET: $h' = \cdot$ and $\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = \cdot$, so $heap = h' + f$ trivially and $\Phi \vdash \cdot \Leftarrow \cdot$ (by `HEAP_EMPTY`).
 PROVE: $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \text{done} \langle bool_value \rangle : ret \Rightarrow ret$.
- ⟨2⟩1. $\cdot \vdash bool_value \Rightarrow \text{bool}$ by `PURE_VAL_TRUE`/`PURE_VAL_FALSE`.
- ⟨2⟩2. $\text{smt}(\cdot \Rightarrow bool_value = \text{aligned}(\tau, mem_ptr))$ by construction of $bool_value$.
- ⟨2⟩3. Prove typing with `EXPL_SPINE_RET`, `EXPL_SPINE_PHI`, `EXPL_SPINE_COMP`, `EXPL_Is_TVAL`.
- ⟨1⟩17. CASE: `EXPL_Is_MEMOP_PTRARRAYSHIFT`.
 PROOF: Similar to `PURE_EXPR_ARRAY_SHIFT`, but with `EXPL_Is_TVAL`.
- ⟨1⟩18. CASE: `EXPL_SEQ_CCALL`.
 ASSUME: $ident:fun \equiv \overline{x_i}^i \mapsto texpr \in \text{Globals}$
 $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \overline{spine_elem_i}^i :: fun \gg ret$.
 $\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}$
 $\langle h + f; \text{ccall}(\tau, ident, \overline{spine_elem_i}^i) \rangle \longrightarrow \langle heap; \sigma_2(texpr):ret' \rangle$
 $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi''; \underline{\mathcal{R}}'' \vdash texpr \Leftarrow ret''$ where $\overline{x_i}^i :: fun \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi''; \underline{\mathcal{R}}'' \mid ret''$.
- PROVE: $\exists h', \Phi', \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ such that
 $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \cdot \sqsubseteq \cdot; \cdot; \Phi'; \cdot$
 $heap = h' + f$
 $\Phi' \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$
 and $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi'; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \sigma_2(texpr) \Leftarrow ret$.
- ⟨2⟩1. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi, \Phi''; \underline{\mathcal{R}}'' \vdash texpr \Leftarrow ret''$
 $\Phi, \sigma_2(\Phi'') \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$
 $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi, \sigma_2(\Phi''); \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \overline{spine_elem_i}^i :: fun \gg ret$.
 PROOF: By lemma B6 (`Weakening`).
- ⟨2⟩2. $ret = ret' = \sigma_2(ret'') \wedge \exists h'_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1$.
 $heap = h'_1 + f$, and $(\Phi, \sigma_2(\Phi'')) \vdash h'_1 \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1$
 $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi, \sigma_2(\Phi''); \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1 \vdash \sigma_2 \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \underline{\mathcal{R}}'')$.
 PROOF: By lemma B9.3 (`Well-typed spines produce substitutions and the same return type`).
- ⟨2⟩3. $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi, \sigma_2(\Phi''); \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1 \vdash \sigma(texpr) \Leftarrow \sigma(ret'')$.
 PROOF: By lemma B7.3 (`Substitution`), because $\sigma_2(\Phi) = \Phi$ since it contains only closed terms / is well-formed w.r.t $\cdot; \cdot$.

⟨2⟩4. LET: $h' = h'_1$; $\Phi' = \Phi, \sigma_2(\Phi'')$; $\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1$.

⟨2⟩5. $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \cdot \sqsubseteq \cdot; \cdot; \Phi, \sigma_2(\Phi''); \cdot$ trivially.

⟨1⟩19. CASE: EXPL_SEQ_PROC.

PROOF: Similar to EXPL_SEQ_PROC.

⟨1⟩20. CASE: EXPL_IS_MEMOP, EXPL_IS_ACTION, EXPL_IS_NEG_ACTION.

PROOF: By induction.

⟨1⟩21. CASE: EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LETP, EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LETTP, EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LET.

PROOF: See EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LET for a more general case and proof.

⟨1⟩22. CASE: EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LETT.

ASSUME: $\cdot; \cdot; \cdot; \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2 \vdash \text{let } \overline{ret_pat}_i^i : ret_1 = \text{done } \langle \overline{ret_term}_i^i \rangle \text{ in } \text{expr}_2 \Leftarrow ret_2$
 so $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1 \vdash \text{done } \langle \overline{ret_term}_i^i \rangle \Leftarrow ret_1$
 and $\Phi \vdash \text{ret_pat} : ret_1 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_3; \mathcal{L}_3; \Phi_3; \underline{\mathcal{R}}_3$
 and $\mathcal{C}_3; \mathcal{L}_3; \Phi, \Phi_3; \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2, \underline{\mathcal{R}}_3 \vdash \text{expr} \Leftarrow ret_2$ (by inversion).

$\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2$ so $h = h_1 + h_2$ where $\Phi \vdash h_1 \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1$ and $\Phi \vdash h_2 \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2$ by lemma B8.4 (Normalised resource context determines structure of heap).

$\langle h + f; \text{let } \overline{ret_pat}_i^i : ret_1 = \text{done } \langle \overline{ret_term}_i^i \rangle \text{ in } \text{expr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{heap}; \sigma(\text{expr}) \rangle$.

where $\langle h; \overline{ret_pat}_i^i = \overline{ret_term}_i^i \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle \text{heap}; \sigma \rangle$.

PROVE: $\exists \Phi', h', \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$.

$\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \cdot \sqsubseteq \cdot; \cdot; \Phi'; \cdot$
 $\text{heap} = h' + f$ and $\Phi' \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$
 $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi'; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \sigma(\text{expr}_2) \Leftarrow \sigma(ret_2)$.

$\exists \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1. \text{heap} = h'_1 + h_2 + f$

$\Phi \vdash h'_1 \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1$ and $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1 \vdash \sigma \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \mathcal{R}')$

by lemma B9.4 (Well-typed values pattern-match successfully).

This means $\cdot; \cdot; [\text{id}, \sigma](\Phi, \Phi_3); \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2 \vdash [\text{id}, \sigma] \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2, \mathcal{R}')$ by lemma B6 (Weakening).

LET: $\Phi' = \Phi, \sigma(\Phi_3)$, $h' = h'_1 + h_2$ and $\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = \underline{\mathcal{R}}'_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2$.

By lemma B7.3 (Substitution), because $\sigma(\Phi) = \Phi$ since it contains only closed terms / is well-formed w.r.t $\cdot; \cdot$.

⟨1⟩23. CASE: EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LETT.

ASSUME: $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2 \vdash \text{let } \overline{ret_pat}_i^i : ret_1 = \text{expr}_1 \text{ in } \text{expr}_2 \Leftarrow ret_2$

so $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1 \vdash \text{expr}_1 \Leftarrow ret_1$

and $h = h_1 + h_2$ where $\Phi \vdash h_1 \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1$ and $\Phi \vdash h_2 \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2$ by lemma B8.4

(Normalised resource context determines structure of heap).

$\langle h; \text{expr}_1 \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{heap}; \text{expr}'_1 \rangle$.

Proceed by induction, instantiating the frame from the inductive hypothesis with $h_2 + f$.

(1)24. CASE: EXPL_TOP_SEQ_CASE.

$$\text{ASSUME: } \cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{case pval of } \overline{\text{pat}_i \Rightarrow \text{texpr}_i}^i \text{ end} \Leftarrow \text{ret}$$

$$\frac{\text{pat}_i; \beta_1 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_i \text{ with } \text{term}_i^i}{\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_i; \mathcal{L}; \Phi, \text{term}_i = \text{pval}; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{texpr}_i \Leftarrow \text{ret}^i}.$$

$$\text{pat}_j = \text{pval} \rightsquigarrow \sigma_j \text{ and } \forall i < j. \text{not} (\text{pat}_i = \text{pval} \rightsquigarrow \sigma_i).$$

LET: $\Phi' = \Phi, \sigma_j(\text{term}_j = \text{pval})$, $h' = h$ and $\underline{\mathcal{R}}' = \underline{\mathcal{R}}$.

$\cdot; \cdot; \Phi'; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash [\text{id}, \sigma_j] \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}_j; \cdot; \underline{\mathcal{R}})$ by lemma B9.4 (Well-typed values pattern-match successfully) and lemma B6 (Weakening).

Hence $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi; \cdot \sqsubseteq \cdot; \cdot; \Phi'; \cdot$ and $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi'; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \sigma_j(\text{texpr}_j) \Leftarrow \sigma_j(\text{ret})$ by lemma B7.3 (Substitution).

(1)25. CASE: EXPL_TOP_SEQ_IF.

See EXPL_TOP_SEQ_CASE for more general case and proof.

(1)26. CASE: EXPL_TOP_SEQ_RUN.

PROOF: Similar to EXPL_SEQ_CCALL.

(1)27. CASE: EXPL_TOP_SEQ_BOUND.

PROOF: By induction.

(1)28. CASE: EXPL_TOP_IS_LETS.

PROOF: Similar to EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LETT.